

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

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Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
UPC	Pau Lloret
SIN	Bryan Pellerin

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CES	Centralized Energy Storage
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DES	Distributed Energy Storage
DoA	Description of Action (Annex I of the Grant Agreement)
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EV	Electric Vehicle
FO	Flexibility Operator
IIP	Integrated INVADE Platform
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OCMP	Open capacity Management Protocol
OCP	Open charge Point Protocol
PLC	Power Line Communications / Carrier
PUC	Pilot Use Case
PV	Photo voltaic
V2G	Vehicle to Grid
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Document D.10.6 reports the conclusions obtained during the pilots and the collected data analysis in T10.3-7.

This deliverable gives an overview of all the results from each of the 5 pilots in a structured way. The reference for the results and the performance reported is based on key performance indicators (KPIs) that were defined in D10.2. These KPIs are based on expected improvements from using the INVADE concept/platform. The results shown in this deliverable have been achieved through the architecture developed in the project, including the use of the INVADE platform to support this architecture. The integration of renewables and storage assets coupled with the introduction of new grid tariff structures mandates the need for use of an optimized control-plan. The INVADE platform, IIP, predicts and suggests this optimized control plan based on the harvested data from the different pilots DER's or existing ecosystem. Through these KPI tests, we aim to prove the net benefit of using INVADE. The test steps are specified in detail, following a uniform procedure and showing test-setups.

All 5 pilots differ greatly in infrastructure and needs, while they are located in 5 different countries with deviant requirements and regulations. For this reason, there are specific KPIs reflecting the individual targets/goals, in addition to the general KPIs that are standardized across all pilots.

The first general KPI 1, demonstrates that the “timeframe” for adapting new customers is almost “0” by using standard protocols and methods. This was met both by using the Asset-loader and with use of an API. After testing the adaption of new customers, the Asset-loader seems to be the favourite option selected by most pilots.

In the Norwegian pilot (Lyse) there is an existing ecosystem built around Smartly AS, who provides energy services to existing customers, where flexibility is part of the service exchange. They are focusing mainly on residential buildings but have also started to move towards larger commercial buildings and housing cooperatives. In Lyse's pilot, the Integrated INVADE platform (IIP) is connected on top of the Smartly-system, where the benefit of using the Asset-loader is demonstrated by easily onboarding new customers. Smartly is the acting Flexibility Operator (FO) in the Norwegian pilot who can control its clients' batteries and their flexible loads. In this way, the pilot-owner Lyse can test peak-shaving and different tariff-optimizations depending on control-plans from the IIP. These tests are conducted using a categorization of different customer profiles: A, B, C, D...

These profiles represent customers with different available distributed energy resource (DER) assets, such as water heaters, floor-heating, electric vehicle (EV) chargers, batteries and PV-panels. Batteries are tested for different purposes, like peak-shaving, for time of use tariff, self-balancing, maximum power control. The battery also directly increases the power quality and reduce noise (like the odd harmonics).

In the Dutch pilot (Elaad and Greenflux), the main task is to test the use of the IIP to suggest control plans for optimizing EV-charging and reduce the grid-load (overload), and to minimize the charging cost. This is tested both on a network of public charging stations, grouped together to represent neighbourhoods, as well as on large commercial parking spaces. A surprising finding in this test is a reduction of the net average power peak-consumption for combined households by approximately 60%. The pilot also tests vehicle-to-grid (V2G) using a DC-charger, still the only available technology on the market. Here, Elaad have successfully tested the bidirectional charging with good results. Elaad tested the reverse energy-flow up to 10kW, with the Nissan Leaf, feeding into their office-building. The KPI 4.6, *optimizing the share of renewables by using the IIP platform* shows that renewable share where effectively used, and the share increased dramatically. The IIP platform will predict the needs from the EV-battery, and the impact of the net-grid consumption.

In the German pilot (Badenova), residential customers are equipped with PV panels, batteries and a home automation system from SMA. Here, the IIP connects to the SMA system, where this harvested data is used to return optimized control plans back to the SMA system. This test demonstrates the value of the IIP's predictions and optimization. In the KPI 5.2, the German pilot demonstrates the possibility to optimize control of the distributed energy storage (DES) assets via the IIP in a very accurate way. On a higher level, the pilot demonstrates that the DES can support the balance in the grid's energy-flow. In 4.6 the German pilot also tested the use of a centralized energy storage (CES) to support the grid. This test was completed in a long/weak LV-feeder, where a large PV-plant is connected in the very end of the line. Without the CES, the voltage increase would result in damage of equipment, and therefore a need for grid investment. By using the CES, the grid operator avoids this investment and can use the battery to stabilize the grid when the PV production varies, also due to for example sudden production disappearance caused by passing clouds.

In the Bulgarian pilot (Albena), the focus has been to control the energy-flow, where the resort-town has a very high energy-demand for hot water heating in its 43 hotels.

The IIP platform generates optimized control plans according to electricity market prices and a prediction of DER production. The savings potential here has been demonstrated to be significant. The cost reduction reached more than 13% in July and August, for the selected hotels, due to the IIP-platform optimization. This is possible by reducing the consumption in high-price periods and increase consumption in low-price periods. They have also invested in a CES to increase their usage of renewables and increase their power quality in Hotel Flamingo.

Finally, in the Spanish pilot, the DSO EPESA is testing the benefits of installing a CES at the substation level. This CES is partly reserved as an UPS for the DSO's main building and grid operations control-room. And also, partly available to provide flexibility and other energy services. In addition to operating according to standards and staying within operational, the battery management system (BMS) can communicate with and receive control-plans from the IIP-platform. The CES responds to flexibility requests from the DSO to relieve predicted congestions and ensure power quality, and flexibility requests from the BRP to reduce imbalances in its portfolio. Additionally, the specific KPI 7 shows that the CES replaces the need of using diesel-generator backup, and hence decreases CO2 emissions.

1 Introduction

This document shows the results of all KPI tests in INVADE, from all 5 pilots.

All KPIs have a systematic structure that makes it easy to compare results from one KPI to another, and with results from other pilot.

The KPIs are divided into two main categories. The general KPIs, common for all pilots, and the specific KPIs with individual goals.

The general KPIs are mostly following the common INVADE project goals at a general level and describes each pilots approach towards these goals. These goals are fundamental goals of the INVADE project.

The specific KPIs are defined specifically for each pilot based on their installations and have more business-oriented goals that are important to this specific pilot.

All KPIs are systematic described, into test steps, and should be easy to follow. All KPI test are summed up in a “conclusion”, one by one.

At the end of each KPI- test, there is a conclusion based on this specific KPI.

2 Norway: Pilot in Stavanger

The Lyse pilot investigates and demonstrates the intersection between V2H/loads/PV, effect-based tariffs and energy management in private homes and buildings, and how they are combined in new business models.

From a business point of view, we believe that these kinds of services at a household level will create both customer value as downstream services in the retail market and future upstream services on a DSO level.

The KPIs will prove the effect and benefit of smart management of energy-efficient components in the home in order to better utilize energy consumption. It is expected that the KPIs will provide the necessary answers to how energy efficient a home can be by using new technology and the INVADE platform.

General KPIs

2.1 Test: Prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”

2.1.1 Purpose

To prove the benefits of using open standard protocols and reducing the possibilities of brand specific customizations. It is important to avoid local “tailor-made” solutions that will influence on the scalability, both in time and in re-structuring of register/database.

2.1.2 Abstract

In this subchapter, the workflow is described adding new recipients of flexibility service to the existing INVADE integrated platform (IIP). The Norwegian pilot is an existing ecosystem, Smartly AS, with existing customers who are provided with energy related services within flexibility. The integration with IIP is used to reduce time of adaptation of new customers for use of AI and machine learning to improve energy consumption. We still have some manual work to set up new customers, but this is at the same level and as time-consuming as setting up the existing services provided by Smartly AS.

The onboarding of new customers to the IIP could be done in three different ways: 1. Manually in the platform. 2. By using Asset Loader. 3. Onboarding by using API. The

Norwegian pilot has mainly done the onboarding of customers by using the Asset loader, but by using the full IIP API the time for setting up customers will be 0.

2.1.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

The test steps are based on using the Asset loader which is a tool provided by the INVADE platform to onboard new customers without using the full API. The tool is based on import and export of excel files. A template has been filled out with Asset ID on all the different devices from each pilot site and uploaded to the INVADE platform. This file import function creates the setup of the sites, assets and contracts for the pilot customers. Installations are made ready for test and are supporting the test steps. The tests were conducted from the perspective of a flexibility operator using the platform as a software tool for providing flexibility services to existing customers of the local ecosystem Smartly.

The existing customers at Smartly are households and housing associations that have installed PV-generation systems, batteries, EV-Chargers, water heaters and floor heating in different combinations. The Smartly ecosystem already have rulesets for controlling devices for optimization of consumption as a service (flexibility services) and collects all the data from each pilot site. The API integration between the platforms ensure that the data from households are sent to the IIP which support with AI and machine learning. Based on the data and contract the IIP creates a control plan for each household for optimization.

2.1.4 Test steps

Table 1. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Add new flexibility provider(customer)	Flexibility customer established within 15 minutes	Successful
2	Define contract between FO and flex provider	Contract established within 5 minutes	Successful
3	Check communication through open standards and protocols between provider and FO according to contract defined	Recipient can execute and communicate instructions according to contracts (latency 5 seconds)	Successful
4	Check communication based open standards and protocols between flex provider and FO according to contract defined	FO can execute and communicate instructions according to contract	Successful

5	Repeat steps 1-3 for 5 different, randomly picked recipients	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	Successful
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Definitions:

- Flexibility provider: Household with PV-generation, EV-charger, battery, water heater and floor heating, Setup varies with different setup in different profiles.
- FO: flexibility Operator: Smartly ecosystem.
- Contract: electronic document to be signed by agreeing parties.

2.1.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values.

The KPI is measured in minutes, from assets occur in 3. party (Smartly) to the asset data is provisioned in the Smartly platform and the customer and asset data is provisioned in the IIP.

2.1.6 Baseline (quantified)

Baseline for the test is the manual process for adapting new customers to the IIP. A manual customer setup takes 30 minutes. Process for adding new customers to the IIP according to test steps by using the Asset Loader:

1. Asset Loader document must be created with input from the Smartly platform: Assets, ID Keys, etc. Asset loader document is sent to the INVADE platform. Sites and assets are created according to the asset loader document. See figure below of hierarchic structure created by the asset loader in the IIP
2. Contract is signed electronically by email followed by acceptance.
3. Verify data in the IIP.

Figure 1: Example of a site with assets created by the asset loader

2.1.7 Target value (with threshold)

The Target value for this KPI is according to expected results in table 1. The threshold is set to 100%.

2.1.8 Reached value

Values met according to table 1.

2.1.9 Conclusion

The results show that there is a great improvement by using the Asset Loader compared with the manual setup of new customers. The manual setup could be used for large installations and still be in line within budget of setting up a new customer with the IIP. For small households or end customers the Asset Loader must be the minimum solution enabling fast scale up with more customers. There is room for improvement, but as a starting point for some FOs with ambitions of scaling up with customers this could be the first step. The second step could be full API integration.

Based on the experience from the project so far, with many customers connected to the IIP, onboarding by using the IIP API must be the standard in the long term. Manual work always increases the chance of errors. Onboarding by using the API, the timeline is “0” and chances for errors is “0”.

2.2 Test: Demonstrate the improvements using batteries.

2.2.1 Purpose

This is a comparative test in order to demonstrate improvement of using batteries through better % usage, lower safety margin and maximum utilization in the installation to reduce power-peaks.

2.2.2 Abstract

KPIs proving the reduction of the vulnerability in latency by using batteries in households.

$KPI = \text{actual response} / \text{theoretical response with no latency}$

This implies that the response time for compensation of loss of power is measured and compared to a pilot requirement or theoretical standard.

2.2.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

“Theoretical response” has been defined.

Ampere meter connected to the battery.

2.2.4 Test steps

Table 2. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Send activation signal from FO. Start clock at point of activation.	Activation executed. Clock started.	Successful
2	Monitor the amp meter connected to the battery. Record time to amp meter change- Record the response time and meter reading at activation.	Response time reading Amp meter reading	Successful
3.	Compare with theoretical measure	Ratio	Successful

2.2.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values.

The measurement procedure to evaluate the benefits of using batteries in household is defined in the previous table. These tests intend to verify the possibility of real-time API control of the batteries and therefore improvements due to better utilization of energy consumption through the different use cases defined in the pilot. The first test applied in this case intends to verify the immediateness of the battery API control, while the second test intends to verify the technical possibility of the battery to supply a load in island mode

for a certain period. The island mode is not a part of our pilot, but the batteries used could support such functionality. The battery has a dedicated output with limited power for critical loads, but the functionality is not yet enabled by the supplier, Eaton.

Figure 2: Time measurement using clock and amp meter during the test

Figure 3: Amp meter measurement on fuse to see when the battery

2.2.6 Baseline (quantified)

This scenario does not have a quantifiable baseline. We use a theoretical response with no latency “0” as the Baseline.

2.2.7 Target value (with threshold)

The targets in this indicator are based on practical measurement of latency from activation from FO to a battery working at the household as requested from the FO. The objective is to verify that the latency between the control signal sent from the FO and the battery activation is according to solve the use cases for the Norwegian pilot described in D10.1. The measurements were done in milliseconds.

- Test 1
 - Latency cloud to battery = From signal is sent from platform to battery activated
 - Latency Activation = From signal is sent to battery and battery start Charging/Discharging
 - Latency Charge = From battery start to request capacity achieved
 - Latency Discharge = From battery start to request capacity achieved
 - Power off = From active battery Charging/discharging to standby

Figure 4: sketch of measurement setup

- Test 2 (simulate black out): the objective is to verify the usage of the battery as back up support in case of an electrical failure. NA in our pilot.

2.2.8 Reached value

Step one and two were successfully executed, with the measurements as in the table in figure 5 below. 4 different requested capacities were tested and measured: Use of 25, 50, 75 and 100 % of the charge/discharge capacity of the battery. The table shows that the battery varies in the latency between charge and discharge. Discharging functionality has a shorter latency than the charging functionality. From activation of battery by the FO to achieved requested capacity at the household it takes an average of approximately 10 seconds.

Table 3: Latency tests done at pilots' site

2000ms	4800ms	0 - 25	12800ms	8600ms	3200ms
2000ms	4800ms	0 - 50	13100ms	7800ms	3200ms
2000ms	4800ms	0 - 75	11100ms	10300ms	3200ms
2000ms	4800ms	0-100%	11100ms	11600ms	3200ms
*Latency cloud to battery = From signal is sent from platform to battery activated					
*Latency Activation = From signal is sent to battery and battery start Charging/Discharging					
*Latency Charge = From battery start to requested capacity achieved					
*Latency Discharge = From battery start to requested capacity achieved					
*Power off = From active battery Charging/discharging to standby					

Figure 5 below shows the measured latency during the test from activation signal is sent from the Smartly platform until the battery has reached the requested power of discharging. The different graphs could be divided into 3 different stages.

1. From Smartly platform to battery,
2. From battery receive control signal until it starts discharging,
3. from battery starts until it has reached the requested power: 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%.

The divided results can be seen in figure 5.

Figure 5: Measured latency discharge

Figure 6 below shows the latency when activation signal is sent from the Smartly platform until the battery has reached the requested power of charging. The different graphs could be divided into 3 different stages.

1. From Smartly platform to battery,
2. From battery receive control signal until it starts charging,

3. From battery starts until it has reached the requested power: 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%.

Figure 6: Measured latency charging

Figure 7: Latency divided in stages. 1 – 4: 25, 50, 75 and 100%

2.2.9 Conclusion

The current test shows that a home battery can be remotely controlled by an FO with a latency which is acceptable according to operational standards within optimization of energy consumption at the household level. This means that a flexibility operator can remote control a home battery to optimize energy consumption at the same level as a local energy management system at the household. It also means that an end customer can use a cloud based, third party as the IIP for optimization of energy consumption. The time from activation signal was sent from the FO it took 4,8 seconds for the battery to

start. The latency measured in this KPI is not only a consequence of the FO controlling the battery, but also related to controlling software and hardware in the battery inverter. Signal from FO to battery took 2 seconds, battery to start took 2,8 seconds. A battery needs time to start and reach a requested value for charging and discharging. Since the power-peaks and tariffs are based on an hourly basis the latency measured is successful.

2.3 Test: Peak reduction VS cost with using “large” inverters.

2.3.1 Purpose

This will prove how households will have very quick ROI when power-tariffs will be introduced. Based on a larger inverter to improve efficiency and reduce power-peaks / costs.

2.3.2 Abstract

This recommendation will reflect the sizing of the battery due to different kinds of connected basic loads, and fast-acting loads with limited duration.

Battery cost = energy capacity * unit cost

This KPI reflects the size in kWh vs peaks (lengths & heights).

KPI = peak reduction / battery cost [kW/€]

Battery inverter 6kW

2.3.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

“Normal” or default consumption is defined for test objects.

SOC status is 100% (80%) before all activations.

Test in new households (passive houses)

Meter readings are known prior to activation.

Concrete KPI must be defined prior to the test.

2.3.4 Test steps

Table 4. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Disconnect all other phases except the battery itself. Ensure that the battery SOC is 100% (80%). Read the meter. Use a stopwatch to measure the time. Discharge the battery until 10% SOC. Stop the watch to check discharge time, read the meter to see how much energy the battery has delivered.	Time should be 27 minutes. Measured energy should be 2,73 kWh.	34 minutes 2,9 kwh
2.	Disconnect all other phases except the battery itself. Ensure that the SOC is 10%. Read the meter, use a stopwatch to measure the time. Charge the battery up to 100% (80%). Stop the watch to check charge time, read the meter to check consumed energy.	Time should be 30,8 minutes Measured energy should be 3,09 kWh.	44 minutes 3 kwh

2.3.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

These pilots with Eaton batteries have a capacity of 6/6 kW on the inverters, the storage max Capacity is 4,2 kW. A battery is normally charged up to 80% SOC and minimum 10%. The inverter has an estimated energy loss for each charge /discharge sequence at 5%. This gives us an available capacity of 2,73 kW and an estimated max peak move capacity on 2,52 kWh. With maximum SOC and maximum throughput the battery is estimated to be engaged in maximum 27 minutes.

The KPI are measured based on how many kWh a peak can be moved from high load period to a low load period which is estimated to 2,52kWh.

The energy price for subscribed effect below subscription limit is 0,02666€/kW and 0,125€/kW above the limit (Lyse Elnett - DSO). For each the kW moved below the limit the customer saves 0,09834€ (energy price not included).

For every day/night the estimated energy savings is calculated to be 2,52kWh * 0,09834€ * 2 cycles = 0,5€.

Battery cost 3.555€.

ROI for a battery investment is calculated to 3555 (battery cost) /0,5€/day = 7110 days. This gives us ROI after 19,5 years.

2.3.6 Target value (with threshold)

Measure the number of kWh a battery consumes from 10% SOC to 80% SOC (estimated 5% energy loss for each charge/discharge sequence in the inverter). Target value is estimated to 3,08 kWh.

Measure the number of kWh a battery can deliver from 80% SOC to 10% SOC. Target is estimated to 2,73 kWh.

2.3.7 Reached value

We have measured the number of kWh a battery consumes when charging from 10% SOC and up to 80% SOC. The measured value is 3 kWh. The time measured was 44 minutes. Results from the Discharging of battery from 80% SOC to 10% SOC measures 2,9 kWh. The time measured was 34 minutes. See figure 8.

Figure 8: Comparison measured time vs estimated time

Figure 9: Comparison measured power vs estimated power

2.3.8 Conclusion

The measured numbers give us a higher max peak move capacity than estimated. The measured max peak move capacity is 3 kW.

For every day/night the calculated energy savings is measured to be $3\text{kWh} * 0,09834\text{€} * 2 \text{ cycles} = 0,59\text{€}$.

ROI for a battery investment is calculated to $3555 \text{ (battery cost)} / 0,59\text{€/day} = 6025 \text{ days}$. This gives us ROI after 16,5 years, and 15,4% better result than estimated.

2.4 Test: Peak reduction VS cost using “smaller” inverters

2.4.1 Purpose

In chapter 3.3 we tested with a 6kW inverter. With hourly based AMS meter readings and hourly based effect tariffs it could be enough with a smaller inverter.

This chapter will prove how households will have very quick ROI when power-tariffs will be introduced based on a smaller inverter to improve efficiency and reduce power-peaks / costs.

2.4.2 Abstract

With a 6kW inverter the 4,2kWh battery is estimated to be engaged in 27 minutes until it reached SOC at 10%. A smaller inverter with lower cost could be sufficient to reach the

same peak move capacity as described in chapter 3.3. The test should prove that a 3,6-kW inverter could move the same capacity within one hour.

The calculated test as the one above. Same as the KPI above, but with a smaller inverter, and move usage in time.

KPI = base reduction / battery cost [kWh/€] = unit battery cost

Battery inverter 3,6kW

2.4.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

KPI is defined prior to test.

2.4.4 Test steps

Table 5. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Disconnect all other phases except the battery itself. Ensure that the battery SOC is 100% (80%). Read the meter. Use a stopwatch to measure the time. Discharge the battery until 10% SOC. Stop the watch to check discharge time, read the meter to see how much energy the battery has delivered.	Time should be 45 minutes. Measured energy should be 2,73 kWh.	56 minutes 2,9 kWh
2	Disconnect all other phases except the battery itself. Ensure that the SOC is 10%. Read the meter, us a stopwatch to measure the time. Charge the battery up to 100% (80%). Stop the watch to check charge time, read the meter to check consumed energy.	Time should be 51,5 minutes Measured energy should be 3,09 kWh.	73 minutes 3 kWh

2.4.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values.

These pilots with Eaton batteries have a capacity of 3,6/3,6 kW on the inverters, the storage max Capacity is 4,2 kW. A battery is normally charged up to 80% SOC and minimum 10%. The inverter has an estimated energy loss for each charge /discharge sequence at 5%. This gives us an available capacity of 2,73 kW and an estimated max peak move capacity on 2,52 kWh. With maximum SOC and maximum throughput the battery is estimated to be engaged in maximum 45 minutes.

The KPI are measured based on how many kWh a peak can be moved from high load period to a low load period which is estimated to 2,52kWh.

The energy price for subscribed effect below subscription limit is 0,02666€/kW and 0,125€/kW above the limit (Lyse Elnett - DSO). For each kW moved below the limit the customer saves 0,09834€ (energy price not included).

For every day/night the estimated energy savings is calculated to be $2,52\text{kWh} * 0,09834€ * 2 \text{ cycles} = 0,5€$.

Battery cost is 3184€

ROI for a battery investment is calculated to $3184 \text{ (battery cost)} / 0,5€/\text{day} = 6368 \text{ days}$. This gives us ROI after 17,4 years.

2.4.6 Target value (with threshold)

Measure the number of kWh a battery consumes from 10% SOC to 80% SOC (estimated 5% energy loss for each charge /discharge sequence in the inverter). Target value is estimated to 3,08 kWh.

Measure the number of kWh a battery can deliver from 80% SOC to 10% SOC. Target is estimated to 2,73 kWh.

2.4.7 Reached value

We have measured the number of kWh a battery consumes when charging from 10% SOC and up to 80% SOC. The measured value is 3 kWh. The time measured was 73 minutes. Results from the Discharging of battery from 80% SOC to 10% SOC measures 2,9 kWh. The time measured was 56 minutes.

Figure 10: Comparison measured time vs estimated time

Figure 11: Comparison measured power vs estimated power

2.4.8 Conclusion

The measured numbers give us a higher max peak move capacity than estimated. The measured max peak move capacity is 3 kWh.

For every day/night the calculated energy savings is measured to be $3\text{kWh} * 0,09834\text{€} * 2 \text{ cycles} = 0,59\text{€}$.

ROI for a battery investment is calculated to $3184 \text{ (battery cost)} / 0,59\text{€/day} = 5396 \text{ days}$. This gives us ROI after 14,7 years, and 15% better result than estimated.

However, a battery with a discharge time of 73 minutes gives us a real discharge capacity within one hour to be 82% of available battery power. Than you do not have the possibility to use all available energy within one peak hour. If the AMS reading resolution in the future changes to a higher frequency (e.g. 15 minutes) a 3,6-kW inverter do not have enough capacity to do peak shave for effect purposes.

2.5 Test: V2G – DC/Chademo

2.5.1 Purpose

Proving the new possibilities within the OCPP 2.0 and 15118 (ed. 2), giving the possibilities to balance the grid when including the reverse energy-flow.

2.5.2 Abstract

Same KPI as above, but now introducing DC-charging with OCPP 2.0, with reverse energy-flow. Again, reduce the risk of exploit the Grid / “living on the edge” without increasing the risk of black-outs, and to avoid “comfort-curtailing” when EV is connected.

2.5.3 Assumptions and Pre-Conditions

- We need EV's in the pilot that are capable of reverse energy-flow charging
 - The Norwegian Pilot acquired a Nissan Leaf for this purpose
 - We use internal cars, from our own employees, not to expose customers to any damage in this test.
- We use a prototype DC-charger from Schneider Electric, to implement this V2G testing.

2.5.4 Test steps: new asset, area and zone

Table 6. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Charge EVs without the external control using the V2G charger. Monitor the raise in SOC (SOC profile amp & V) Monitor the accumulated load Compare results to regular chargers	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	ok
2	Repeat step 1 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	ok
3	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity and a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours)	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	Not possible
4	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions, using a standardised day-routine of charging-discharging-charging	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	Not possible
5	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours) and the INVADE optimizer, taking into account both charging and discharging as possible performance of charger.	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	Not possible
6	Compare results of all steps	KPI $\geq 1-V2/V1 \geq 0,3$	

2.5.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

Since V2G charging stations are a new technology and difficult to find, we did this test together with Schneider France and their V2G prototype. The Charger was shipped to Norway and installed in the garage at the Lyse head office. The prototype contained all the necessary measurement equipment to fulfil this task.

2.5.6 Baseline (quantified)

This scenario does not have a quantifiable baseline.

2.5.7 Target value (with threshold)

The target of this test is to measure reverse-energy flow to reduce power peaks. The target value is 10 kW reverse-energy flow.

2.5.8 Reached value

During the test we reached a 10kW reverse-energy flow for 5 seconds. This meaning that a V2G can be used for energy related solutions and services when the technology is more mature.

2.5.9 Conclusion

In lack of technology, standardisation and development within V2G it has been difficult to deliver completely as expected in the DoA when it comes to V2G. The pilot has a V2G setup at the Lyse HQ to do the testing and validation. The V2G has been tested with 10 kW reverse energy-flow for 5 seconds. The first two Nissan Leaf's tested had an inverter breakdown and damage on the cars. Both cars had to be transported to a garage for repair. One of them needed a replacement of the main charger in the car (5000-euro repair). The third car was tested successfully for 5 seconds with 10 kW reverse energy-flow. Since the cars were owned by employees at Lyse, no risk was taken in testing more cars. Nissan did not provide any battery warranty on the cars during the test.

The outcome of the short test with the third car is that reverse-energy flow with V2G has been tested, and this solution is to "complicated" / immature and too expensive. Future V2G AC-chargers will most likely replace today's V2G DC-chargers.

2.6 **Test: measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling by including a battery**

2.6.1 **Purpose**

This KPI will measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling of including a battery as part of an installation. This should be done at both for at household level, building level and on substation level.

2.6.2 **Abstract**

KPI will prove the quality-improvement of including the battery in the installation. Reflecting the standards of quality measuring like:

Limiting max. voltage level on grid connection point to a given level given by law or standard.

2.6.3 **Assumptions and pre-conditions**

In many countries maximum and minimum voltage levels are given by law or standard.

Regulated by law the DSO`s in Norway must follow voltage level set by NVE. The Slow variations in the effective value of the voltage shall be within an interval of $\pm 10\%$ of the rated voltage, measured as an average over one minute. In a grid with a nominal voltage of 230 V the voltage must be in the range 207V - 253V. But on the grid connection point of distributed energy sources the max. voltage increase is limited to a much lower value of +3%.

At the test site the voltage baseline was 233V, with no electric load behind the main meter. The household is close to the substation for the area, and that is probably the reason for the relatively high voltage baseline.

The battery from Eaton does not have an automatic voltage control system by default, so the test steps and measurements are manually performed.

2.6.4 Test steps

Table 7. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Identify day expecting significant voltage increases due to high PV-generation and low load (e.g. sunny Sunday afternoon).	Sunday afternoon 12.00	successful
2	Track activation of automatic local voltage control using online monitoring.	Start and stop of charge of battery, manually	successful
3	Local voltage control is activated	Charge battery started	Successful
4	Track, if local voltage control is able to reach the preselected target value, which is lower than 230V+3%.	Voltage decreases and reach target value	Successful
5	Track, how much energy flow from the battery is needed to keep the preselected target value over the time.	kWh	Successful

2.6.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

This KPI will measure during both increasing and decreasing of the voltage level. The measurement done during one minute per charging/discharging cycle to pinpoint the slow variations in the effective value of the voltage range described in chapter 3.6.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions. The measurement was done with a voltage meter during battery charge and discharge. Battery was set to charge and discharge with different power 10 – 100% of nominal power, to measure changes in the voltage level with a voltage meter.

Noise (odd harmonics) measuring THD was measured with an instrument provided by the local DSO. Measurement procedure was the same as with the voltage level. THD meter connected during battery charge and discharge over a period of time.

2.6.6 Baseline (quantified)

The baseline for this test is the voltage measured without any load behind the meter, a sunny afternoon on a Sunday. Baseline measured 233 V.

2.6.7 Target value (with threshold)

The target of this test is to measure decrease of voltage using battery installed at a household. The factor for this scenario is set to lower than 230V+3%. (236,9V). Since the baseline is 233V the preselected target value is set to 226V.

The target of the Noise (odd harmonics) measurement is to see if the battery cause or solve problems within noise and odd harmonics.

2.6.8 Reached value

The table 8, and bar chart in figure 12 shows the measured voltage values from the test during different power levels from the battery. The test includes both increase and decrease of voltage level by using the battery. As in table 8 below the target value was met by charging the battery with 6 kW. The test shows improvement of increased voltage quality by 3% ($233-226=7$ ($7/233*100 = 3\%$))

Table 8: Measurement and notes from test

Power	Voltage test/ improvement of voltage			baseline
	Capacity	Discharge	Charge	
0,6 kW	10 %	234	231	233
1,5 kW	25 %	235	232	233
3,0 kW	50 %	236	229	233
4,5 kW	75 %	238	228	233
6,0 kW	100 %	239	226	233

Figure 12: Bar chart of measured values

The measurement in the charts below shows the measured THd during the test. The first chart shows measurement during the test, and the second chart shows the THd during a period of time to find the average THd at the pilot site. The reached values in the first chart show a slight increase in noise (odd harmonics) and very low impact from the

battery. The limit value for Thd is 8%. As measured during a period of time the average Thd is 1%. The average Thd during battery charge and discharge was 1,2 %.

Figure 13 Thd measured during test

Figure 14 Thd average over a period

2.6.9 Conclusion

This test shows that the battery used in the pilot can improve the voltage quality by 3% with charging power of 6kW from the battery. This is quite impressive and important for

a DSO to be aware of. The test also show that the battery could be used as-a-service towards the DSO, which must provide voltage quality as described in 3.6.3: The Slow variations of the voltage within an interval of $\pm 10\%$ of the rated voltage, measured as an average over one minute. The voltage as an average over one minute also fit very well with the results in the latency test 2.2.8 which prove that the battery has a relatively fast response within seconds to support voltage improvement as well as peak having and optimization of energy consumption.

The results from the test could in worst case be a concern for some DSO's. To many batteries connected to one substation could cause problems for the voltage level as well as solving it. The voltage level at the substation level is a fixed setting and cannot be remote-controlled. For a TSO or BRP controlling batteries for their business it could cause problems for the DSO and their commitment to voltage quality.

Noise (odd harmonics) there can be seen a slight increase, but it is so low in advance that it takes very little to make a small change. The impact from the battery system is very small and in a grid with slightly higher level with interference from other appliances it would not have been possible to see the impact of the battery.

2.7 Test: Optimize energy consumption based on hourly rate

As defined in D10.5, the purpose of this test is to compare the impact of switching off the low priority components when the energy price is high.

The existing customers at Smartly are households and housing associations that consists of PV-generation systems, Batteries, EV-Chargers, Water heaters and floor heating in different combinations. The Smartly ecosystem already have rulesets for controlling devices for optimization of consumption as a service and collects all the data from each pilot site. The API integration between the platforms ensure that the data from households are sent to the IIP which support with AI and machine learning. Based on the data and contract the IIP create a control plan for each household for optimization.

This KPI will verify how AI and advanced machine learning can improve energy consumption compared with rule-based algorithms and if the cost of AI and ML will be justifiable in relation to savings.

2.7.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values.

The KPI will be measured in improvement of energy consumption based on hourly rate. How AI and machine learning can improve energy consumption compared with rule-based algorithms. The measurement will be in % and NOK.

The timeline for measuring is ideally if possible, but with limited time, we will measure for one week with rule-based algorithms and one week with AI and machine learning. Main meter data has been collected for one month.

- Profile B
- Profile E

Figure 15: Use of battery to switch load with hourly based tariff

Figure 16: Charging in periods when the price is low

2.7.2 **Baseline (quantified)**

Baseline for the KPI is a measured consumption by the HAN-reader connected to the main meter at pilot site over a period of one week before testing. The baseline data does not include any control of devices for optimization.

2.7.3 **Target value (with threshold)**

The target value for this KPI is 10% improvement of energy consumption by using the IIP compared with Rule-based algorithms.

2.7.4 **Reached value**

The test results are divided in optimizing by using a battery and EV- charging. The battery test shows that there is no difference between the rule-based and the AI based algorithms. The test by using the EV – charger shows that the rule- based algorithms is better than the AI algorithms. The improvement measured is 10 %.

2.7.5 **Conclusion:**

The test shows that there is a minimal improvement by using a battery compared to RIO of a battery. The battery has a limited energy move capacity to comply this use-case.

2.8 **Test: Optimize energy consumption based on effect/power**

As defined in D10.5, the purpose of this test is to quantify the impact of switching off the low priority components to reduce the maximum load (peak shaving) within a predefined duration, in order to reduce the energy bill for the customer where this is applicable

The existing customers at Smartly are households and housing associations that consists of PV-generation systems, batteries, EV-Chargers, water heaters and floor heating in different combinations. The Smartly ecosystem already have rulesets for controlling devices for optimization of consumption as a service and collects all the data from each pilot site. The API integration between the platforms ensure that the data from households are sent to the IIP which support with AI and machine learning. Based on the data and contract the IIP create a control plan for each household for optimization of peak-power reduction.

The KPI in this test shows how AI and machine learning (ML) improve energy consumption compared with rule-based algorithms. And will the cost of AI and ML be justifiable in relation to savings?

To measure the KPIs, it's necessary to list all the meters involved and elaborate a comparison between the data received before and after the implementation of algorithms.

2.8.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values.

The KPI measures in terms of energy consumption reduction due to reduction of power peaks. How AI and machine learning can improve reduction of power peaks compared with rule-based algorithms. The rule-based algorithms are logical rules developed by a human. E.g. If consumption is high, start discharge of battery by 50%. The measurement will be in % and NOK, -

Price model for power-based tariff in the Norwegian pilot.

In this model, it is money saving to keep a consistently low consumption, without too high consumption peaks. In the pricing model, customers subscribe to a given number of KW (power) that they should use at the same time. Subscription power price should be multiplied by the number of KW your subscription limit. The subscription is recommended to each customer is based on historical consumption. If a customer uses more than the subscription, they pay a higher price for it. In our case with the limitation of 5 KW the customer must pay 5 times higher than the normal price per kWh.

In this test the subscribed power limit is 5 kW power, and the price is 26,66 øre (0,27 NOK) per kWh (energy part of the tariff?). Consumed kWh above the subscribed limitation (5Kwh) the price is 125 øre (1,25NOK) per kWh. see example of price development in figure 15.

Figure 17: Price development

Timeline for measuring, ideally as long as possible, but with limited time, we will measure for one week with rule-based algorithms and one week with AI and advanced machine learning. Main meter data has been collected for one month.

- Profile B
- Profile E

Figure 18: Peak shaving by using battery

Figure 19: Peak shaving by smart charging

2.8.2 Baseline (quantified)

Baseline for the KPI is the measured consumption by the HAN-reader connected to the main meter at pilot site over a period of one week before testing. The baseline data does not include any control of devices for optimization.

2.8.3 Target value (with threshold)

The target value for this KPI is 10% improvement of energy consumption by using the IIP compared with Rule-based algorithms.

2.8.4 Reached value

The test results are divided in optimizing by using a battery and EV- charging. The battery test shows that there is no difference between the rule-based and the AI based algorithms. The test by using the EV – charger shows that the rule- based algorithms is better than the AI algorithms. The improvement measured is 10 %.

2.8.5 Conclusion

This KPI show that there is great improvement in reducing power-peaks by using battery and smart EV-charging. The results of the test in figure 18 (battery) and 19 (EV- charger) show how the predicted power peak are moved to the low peak period. The reduction of power peak is limited to the battery capacity calculated in chapter 3.3, and the EV-charging is moved to the low peak period. The savings have been calculated to:

- Battery: $0,49\text{€} * 365 = 178\text{€}$ per year
- EV: $0,93\text{€} * 365 = 343\text{€}$ per year

2.9 Test: Optimize utilization of self-produced energy

As defined in D10.5, the purpose of this test is to reveal the impact of optimal consumption of self-produced solar power and power management throughout the day to get the lowest possible power bill. During this time of year, the solar production is limited. Most of the solar production goes directly to cover some of the baseload at the households. Figure 18 shows the production curve for a pilot.

Figure 20: Production curve January to November

Table 9: Power to grid savings before and after the battery implementation

Type of Pilot	Power to grid before implementation of battery	Power to grid after implementation of battery	Saved Money
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from January	0 kWh to grid	0 kWh to grid	0€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from February	9,16 kWh to grid	0 kWh to grid	0,91€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from March	17,64 kWh to grid	0 kWh to grid	0,18€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from April	87,02 kWh to grid	17,4 kWh to grid	7€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from May	104,72 kWh to grid	20,9 kWh to grid	8,3€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from June	85,84 kWh to grid	17,1 kWh to grid	6,9€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from July	125,81 kWh to grid	25,1 kWh to grid	10€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from August	77,85 kWh to grid	15,5 kWh to grid	6,2€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from September	38,4 kWh to grid	0 kWh to grid	3,8€
PV 1 Based on PV – production data from October	3,5 kWh to grid	0 kWh to grid	0,35€

Figure 21: PV- production, day in October

Figure 22: PV production, day in July

2.9.1 Baseline (quantified):

Baseline for the KPI is the measured consumption by the HAN-reader connected to the main meter at pilot site over a period of one week before testing. The baseline data does not include any control of devices for optimization.

2.9.2 Target value (with threshold):

The target value for this KPI is to increase own consumption by 20% by using battery. Charge the battery when the PV- production is high, and discharge when the consumption is higher than production.

2.9.3 Reached value

The results show that the PV production do not have any impact on Peak-shaving of Power tariffs. The reason for this is that the pilot's energy consumption is below the tariff limit in the solar production timeslot.

Calculations done for the average PV production for the pilots, the data during 2019 shows potential of utilisation of 453 kWh with use of battery combined with PV-production. This will improve ROI of the PV investment estimated to 44€ per year. (2,9 kWp system).

2.9.4 Conclusion

The results show that the PV production do not have any impact on Peak-shaving of Power tariffs. The reason for this is that the pilot's energy consumption is below the tariff limit in the solar production timeslot. Even with PV production data from July the consumption in the solar production timeslot shows that all PV energy was consumed directly or sold back to the grid. The consumption was below the power tariff limit all the time during the PV- production timeslot.

General conclusion based on the KPIs

The different use cases separately have limited savings compared with a combination of the different use cases. Rule-based algorithms have the same savings when it comes to measuring the different use cases separately. The most efficient and cost saving is to combine the different use cases in one solution. This is where AI can give an advantage compared with the rule-based algorithms. The table below shows the total savings in average for all the pilots in Norway which could be combined in one solution. Total savings 586€ by using battery in combination with PV and EV-charging.

Table 10: Savings per use case

Use case	Savings
Optimized own production PV + Battery	44€ per year
Power tariff/ Peak shaving EV + Battery	EV: $0,93€ * 365 = 343€$ per year Battery: $0,49€ * 365 = 178€$ per year
Time of Use EV + Battery	EV: $0,04€ * 365 = 14,6€$ per year Battery: $0,02€ * 365 = 7,3€$ per year

3 The Netherlands

General KPIs

3.1 Test: prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”

3.1.1 Purpose

To prove the benefits of using open standard protocols and reducing the possibilities of brand specific customizations. It is important to avoid local “tailor-made” solutions that will influence on the scalability, both in time and in re-structuring of register/database. Applies to all use-cases.

3.1.2 Abstract

By using open standards, we guarantee access to the platform to everyone who desires to run the platform. Adding a new customer is therefore possible without any boundaries or procedures to follow other than the ones that are under the control of the party that desires to enter a new contract.

The main goal of this test is to show that time spent for adding new flexibility recipients approaches zero. This is done in two different ways: by using the provided asset loader and API integration.

For the asset loader, much of the time needed to create either a flex recipient or provider is still manual work. Using the API integration, no additional manual work is needed, since they have already been created in another platform. Instead, the latency between creation in the platform and the IIP is measured.

3.1.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

This this test, we are testing three different approaches:

- Via the API between the GreenFlux platform and the IIP
- Via the Asset Loader for the IIP
- Manually

Installation ready for test and supporting the test steps.

3.1.4 Test steps

Table 11. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Add new recipient of flexibility	Flexibility customer established within 10 seconds	OK
2	Define contract between FO and flex recipient	Contract established within 2 minutes	OK
3	Check communication through open standards and protocols between recipient and FO according to contract defined	Recipient can execute and communicate instructions according to contracts (latency < 10 seconds)	Optimization profiles are received by chargers within 10 seconds
4	Add new flexibility provider	Flexibility provider established within 10 seconds	OK
5	Define contract between FO and flex provider	Contract established within 2 minutes	OK
6	Check communication based open standards and protocols between flex provider and FO according to contract defined	FO can execute and communicate instructions according to contract (latency < 10 seconds)	OK
7	Repeat steps 1-3 for 5 different, randomly picked recipients	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	OK
8	Repeat steps 4-6 for 50 randomly picked and different recipients	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	No degradation notices. System stable.

3.1.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

3.1.6 Baseline (quantified)

The baseline that was used in this test was the manual configuration of flexibility recipients and flexibility providers. In order to create a flexibility recipient, the following steps need to be taken:

- Create flexibility area;
- Create price area;
- Create weather area;
- Create site;
- Create resource load;
- Create resource generation;
- Create resource EV charger

In order to create a flexibility provider, the following steps need to be taken:

- Create new counterparty;

- Create new contract product;
- Create new product

Since this is manual work, this process takes quite long, as in figure 23 and 24.

Figure 23. Duration of test steps in manual creation of flexibility recipient

Figure 24. Duration of test steps in manual creation of flexibility provider

3.1.7 Target value (with threshold)

The target value for the asset loader is to show that the creation time is decreased rapidly for each additional flex recipient or flex provider that is created. Eventually. The time spent for creating a new recipient or provider should approach zero.

As for the API integration, the latency should be below 2 seconds.

3.1.8 Reached value

Figure 25. Duration of test steps in creating of flexibility recipient using the asset loader

Figure 26. Duration of test steps in manual creation of flexibility provider using the asset loader

Figure 27. Time response after creation of flexibility recipient

Figure 28. Time response after creation of flexibility provider

3.1.9 Conclusion

This test proves that the time spent to create new flexibility recipients and providers approaches zero when using the INVADE asset loader. This save loads time compared to doing this manually. The asset loader makes the IIP accessible for parties that have not (yet) integrated with the IIP but want to test its functionality or use the functionality on a small scale.

The test also proves that the latency between the two systems is also close to zero, meaning there is very efficient communication.

3.2 Test: demonstrate the improvements using batteries

3.2.1 Purpose

Elaad purchased a stationary battery of 137 kWh in order to obtain measurements on electricity fed back into the grid, while waiting for V2G hardware to become available to the project.

The battery was successfully used to decrease the power usage peak to the Elaad office building during the morning. This peak is caused mainly by the 40 charging stations on the premises. Therefore, the battery was not needed during the weekends.

3.2.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

137 kWh will not be sufficient to charge all vehicles.

Power loss during the charging and discharging cycle will occur.

3.2.3 Test steps

Table 12: Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Send activation signal from FO. Start clock at point of activation.	Activation executed. Clock started.	Almost immediate
2	Monitor the amp meter connected to the battery. Record time to amp meter change- Record the response time and meter reading at activation.	Response time reading Amp meter reading	Almost immediate
3.	Rerun test in the following manner: Simulating a black out.	Run new tests after adjustments	Block response, almost immediate
4.	Disconnect power. Simulate black out		Not performed

3.2.4 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

We measured the discharge of the battery in response to the power demand of the office site.

3.2.5 Reached value

As shown in the figure, the battery can be operated to follow the peaks in energy demand of the site (negative values), whilst the charging at night can be controlled at a steady 20 kW power value.

During the runtime of the battery, we found that the power usage required to operate the battery itself (due to ventilation, cooling and the loss of energy during cycles) equals the power usages of approximately 4 households per year. This causes a significant operating cost of the battery.

Figure 29. Charging (+) and discharging (-) of the battery

3.2.6 Conclusion

A battery can be used to reduce the peak power demand of buildings or areas, in order to reduce the strain on the grid. However, the power usage by the battery itself makes the business case for a battery very dependent on the costs of the capacity tariff in place.

3.3 Test: peak reduction using Smart Charging – Individual houses

3.3.1 Purpose

This will prove how peak reduction can be managed within individual households with local renewable energy production using smart charging. Comparing these results to those where a battery is used for peak reduction will provide useful input for the assessment of household battery management systems.

3.3.2 Abstract

In this test, 40 household locations have been connected to the Integrated Invade Platform (IIP) and the GreenFlux platform in order to assess the result of introducing smart charging on the maximum energy consumption peak (kW_{max}).

In this case, all household energy consumption is considered inflexible load, meaning these can't be influenced by the algorithm. The EV chargers are flexible assets and are used in order to use the flexibility. All data is collected in the IIP and used for the prediction of energy consumption, renewable energy production and electric vehicle charging behaviour. Based on these predictions, an optimized charging profile is sent to the charger to influence the net energy consumption profile. This is shown schematically in figure 30.

Normally, all assets must stay within specific limits (grid capacity) in order to avoid grid congestion. In this case, accurate predictions on energy consumption and production profiles are historical data is used. This data is then combined into a new optimal capacity, which is usually lower than the maximum grid capacity, in order to lower the kWmax of the combined assets.

Figure 30. Overview of the data collected and used in the Dutch home pilot

3.3.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

In this case, we assume that the households are representative for normal Dutch households.

3.3.4 Test steps

Table 13: Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Measure household energy consumption data on a 15-minute basis using smart meters	Reliable data measurements	OK
2	Measure renewable energy (solar PV) production data on a 15-minute basis using smart meters	Reliable data measurements	OK

3	Connect assets to IIP	Real-time connection to IIP	OK
4	Connect assets to GreenFlux platform	Real-time connection to GreenFlux platform	OK
5	Generate energy consumption and production predictions	Reliable predictions	OK
6	Introduce smart charging and optimal profiles	Optimal capacity based on renewable energy production	OK
7	Monitor the asset for a period of at least a month in order to evaluate the effects of the new situation	Stable and valid results	OK
8	Repeat this for 39 other households		OK
9	Calculate KPI max peak reduction on individual household basis		OK
10	Calculate KPI max peak reduction on average over all households		OK

3.3.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values (to be updated)

3.3.6 Baseline (quantified)

In figure A1 below the measured baselines are shown for household energy consumption, renewable energy production and electric vehicle charging for one household. These baselines were compiled into the net energy consumption profile, shown in figure.

Similar baselines were measured for another 39 households, resulting in a total of 40 households. Not surprisingly, these look similar.

From the baselines, as briefly discussed in 3.2.6, the following conclusions were drawn:

- A. Electric vehicle charging coincides with household energy consumption peaks.**
The height of the net energy consumption peak is largely dependent on electric vehicle charging behaviour. Changing this behaviour will strongly influence the peak load on the local grid.
- B. Renewable energy production and electric vehicle charging almost never happen simultaneously.**
Renewable energy (PV) is produced when the EV is not charging, and vice versa. Therefore, prosumer optimization for single households was not considered in this test. (Potentially, this issue can be solved using storage systems. However, it should be noted that in order to reduce the electric vehicle charging peak, most likely a large battery is needed).

c. The net energy consumption peak is within the household grid boundary

A typical house in the Netherlands has a max peak load of 17,25 kW at any given moment. Within the baselines for the households, the max load never exceeded 13,46 kW. Therefore, there is no direct need to optimize individual households for the end-user on reducing the grid load. However, in order to compare the individual optimization of the households with the clustered optimization, peak reduction and prosumer optimization was taken as primary optimization objective.

Figure 31. Weekly household energy consumption profiles

Figure 32. Household net energy consumption profile

Figure 33. Sum of all household net energy consumption profiles

3.3.7 Target value (with threshold)

The max peak load in de baseline above is 11,973 kW. The goal of the optimization is to reduce this to below 5 kW.

3.3.8 Reached value

When running the optimization, the max peak load for individual households was reduced by 59% on average, as can be seen in figure 11. The new maximum peak for the households was between 4,2 and 4,7 kW and 4,4 kW on average. Figure shows an example of a typical peak reduction during the day. When the data from all optimized households is combined, the effect of the individual optimization can be demonstrated. This is shown in figure A5. Surprisingly, reducing the net energy consumption of the individual households resulted in a reduction of the maximum peak of the combined household net energy consumption by 64% on average, which is more than was expected. The new maximum peak during the week was shown to be 77 kW.

Figure 34: Peak reduction (%)

Figure 35. Example of peak reduction with/ without optimization

Figure 36. Average peak reduction

3.3.9 Conclusion

Optimizing for max peak reduction reduces the average household net consumption peak by 59%.

The new maximum peak was around 4,4 kW.

Combined with other households in the area, the average net consumption peak was reduced by 64% from 325 kW to 75 kW.

3.4 Test: Peak reduction using Smart Charging – Combined Optimization

3.4.1 Purpose

The purpose of this test is to compare the clustered optimization with the individual optimization as done in 3.3. In order to perform this test, all 40 household locations will be considered and optimized as one flexibility area.

3.4.2 Abstract

Instead of considering the individual max capacity, the maximum capacity of the grid in the area is being considered. By approaching all electric vehicles as one flexible asset, this provides new opportunities for the DSO in order to efficiently manage the grid.

3.4.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

Same as 3.3.3.

3.4.4 Test steps

Table 14. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Measure household energy consumption data on a 15-minute basis using smart meters	Reliable data measurements	OK
2	Measure renewable energy (solar PV) production data on a 15-minute basis using smart meters	Reliable data measurements	OK
3	Connect assets to IIP. Configure as one flexibility area	Real-time connection to IIP	OK
4	Connect assets to GreenFlux platform. Configure as one flexibility area	Real-time connection to GreenFlux platform	OK
5	Generate energy consumption and production predictions	Reliable predictions	OK
6	Introduce smart charging and optimal profiles	Optimal capacity based on renewable energy production	OK
7	Monitor the asset for a period of at least a month in order to evaluate the effects of the new situation	Stable and valid results	OK
8	Calculate KPI max peak reduction		OK
9	Compare results with results in 3.3.		OK

3.4.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values (to be updated)

3.4.6 Baseline (quantified)

The baseline is the same as in 3.3.6. Also, the results from 3.3.8. are considered a baseline for comparison.

3.4.7 Target value (with threshold)

The target value for the maximum peak of the households together is 75 kW.

3.4.8 Reached value

Table 16 shows a comprehensive overview of the resulting averages of the maximum net energy consumption peak of the combined households during a week.

Compared to the original situation, the peaks were significantly reduced. Reductions amounted to 23% on a Saturday) and 79% on a Monday. This is shown in figure 35. The new maximum peak during the week was 69 kW. This is well below the target value, as well as the maximum peak found in 1.2, which was 77 kW. Therefore, it can be concluded that by managing the households together instead of individually can further reduce the maximum load on the grid.

Also, the profile was shown to be much more stable, as can be seen in figure 15.

The own use of renewable energy was also slightly improved. This can be explained by the fact that when more households are considered as one flexible asset, the chances of a car being present while renewable energy is produced by the solar panels is larger and therefore the energy can be assigned to a vehicle of the neighbour for instance.

Table 15: Maximum peak for all households together using different optimization tests

Day	Max peak (kW)		
	No optimization	Individual optimization	Combined optimization
Monday	325 kW	74 kW	67 kW
Tuesday	199 kW	68 kW	69 kW
Wednesday	255 kW	77 kW	67 kW
Thursday	300 kW	77 kW	68 kW
Friday	217 kW	72 kW	69 kW
Saturday	87 kW	60 kW	67 kW
Sunday	125 kW	49 kW	54 kW

Figure 37. Results compared with baseline (no optimization)

Figure 38. Results compared with baseline (individual optimization)

3.4.9 Conclusion:

From this test it can be concluded that the combined optimization of flexible assets at home, in this project done with INVADE platform, is a better way of optimizing than the individual management of the flexible assets. Because this way, the combined maximum net energy consumption can be reduced and locally produced renewable energy can be used more effectively.

3.5 Test: V2G – DC/Chademo

3.5.1 Purpose

Proving the new possibilities within the OCPP 1.6, giving the possibilities to balance the grid when including the reverse energy-flow.

3.5.2 Abstract

Same KPI as above, but now introducing DC-charging with OCPP 1.6, with reverse energy-flow. Again, reduce the risk of exploit the Grid / “living on the edge” without increasing the risk of black-outs, and to avoid “comfort-curtailing” when EV is connected.

3.5.3 Assumptions and Pre-Conditions

- We need a fully functional charging station for V2G, which has proven to be difficult to find.
 - As a fall-back scenario a stationary battery has been purchased. The battery can be operated instead of the Nissan Leaf. The battery has a capacity of 137 kWh, making it comparable to 3 Nissan Leaf V2G cars virtually arriving with

about 70% SOC at the start of a working day. It must be noted that as to date, the purchase of the battery has not yet been approved or compensated by the EC. However, due to the immaturity of V2G as a system, it was necessary to do so to prevent time loss within the project.

- By the end of 2018, Elaad finalized the inventory process on V2G chargers and ordered a 10kW DC V2G charger from the Belgian charge point manufacturer eNovates, which was delivered and installed in February 2019.
- We need EV's in the pilot that are capable of reverse energy-flow charging, these are limited two three types of car (two BEV and 1 PHEV type)
 - Elaad acquired a Nissan Leaf to ensure a suitable car for performing experiments with
- The drivers/owners of the EV's are likely to require extra warranties for usage of their battery for V2G
 - We will be using our own car, which mitigates this pre-condition

OCPP 2.0 was not released in time and thus not available for V2G usage and testing. Nevertheless, V2G will be tested in the Dutch pilot at Elaad premises using OCPP1.6. This will also show the possibilities and possible gaps in the OCPP protocol to support V2G supply. V2G functionality is not included in the official released versions of OCPP1.6 (or OCPP2.0). Based on the tests in the INVADE project Elaad has written a Request for Change (RfC) on how V2G could be included in OCPP. This RfC is handed over to the Open Charge Alliance, the organisation managing the OCPP protocol. With the INVADE RfC as a basis, OCA has decided to start a new working group to formally add V2G functionality to the OCPP protocol.

3.5.4 Test steps: new asset, area and zone

Table 16. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result	Comments
1	Charge EVs without the external control using the V2G charger. Monitor the raise in SOC (SOC profile amp & V) Monitor the accumulated load Compare results to regular chargers	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	OK OK OK	
2	Repeat step 1 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	OK OK	

3	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity and a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours)	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	OK OK OK	This test did not yield much additional insights. When charging at reduced capacity during a fixed time frame, one can predict the resulting SOC 100% accurately
4	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions, using a standardized day-routine of charging-discharging-charging	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	OK	
5	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours) and the INVADE optimizer, taking into account both charging and discharging as possible performance of charger.	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	OK	
6	Compare results of all steps	KPI $\geq 1 - V2/V1 \geq 0,3$	OK	

3.5.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

Since V2G is a new technology for which standard test procedures did not exist prior to the work in INVADE, we developed a new test procedure for testing V2G cars and chargers, which is now the standard in the Netherlands, for both AC and DC V2G, for testing future cars and chargers. The tests for INVADE as well as future tests are carried out in the Dutch testing facilities at the Elaad Test Laboratory premises, which was partly funded by INVADE budget and which was officially opened by Secretary of State Van Veldhoven on April 18th, 2018. See deliverable D10.4 for more information on the Elaad Test Laboratory and on the difficulties encountered during the purchase procedure for the V2G charger.

3.5.6 Specific results for the INVADE V2G Charger

Prior to the arrival of the V2G charger, Elaad used the battery at the office for managing the load for its pilot. See chapter 1.2

The eNovates V2G charger is, like the other chargers used in the INVADE project, registered at the Elaad backoffice, and measurements are first entered in the monitoring system of the Elaad test laboratory. In our system, we are able to view all kinds of real time data, as can be seen in the figure below.

Bus event 323/323: 13:32:50.574

Vehicle to charger			Charger to vehicle			Debug data		
ID	Description	Data	ID	Description	Data	ID	Description	Data
h100.0	Minimum charge current	6A	h108.0.0	Welding detection	compatible	id	state	Charger state
h100.1-2	Total capacity of battery	0kWh/10	h108.1-2	Available output voltage	500V	event	D1 contact	Charger event
h100.4-5	Maximum battery voltage	435V	h108.3	Available output current	25A	lo_st_0	D2 contact	No event
h100.6	Charged rate reference	100	h108.4-5	Threshold voltage	435V	lo_st_1	Connector proximity	closed
h101.1-2	Maximum charging time	78min	h109.0	ChkIdEMO spec	2	lo_st_2	Operation permission	open
h101.3	Estimated charging time	0min	h109.1-2	Present output voltage	384V	lo_st_3	DC connector	locked
h101.5-6	Total capacity of battery	389kWh/10	h109.3	Present output current	0A	lo_st_5	Lock state	locked
h102.0	ChkIdEMO spec	2	h109.4.0	Discharge compatibility	compatible	lock_st	Lock state	locked
h102.1-2	Target battery voltage	410V	h109.5.5	Charging stop control	operating	ch_config.voltage	Voltage setpoint	445.0V
h102.3	Charging current request	25A	h109.5.4	Charging system error	normal	ch_config.current	Current setpoint	-10.0A
h102.4.4	Battery voltage deviation	normal	h109.5.3	Battery incompatibility	compatible	ch_config.enabled	Charger enabled	off
h102.4.3	High battery temperature	normal	h109.5.2	Lock energizing state	locked	ch_status.voltage	Voltage	384.5V
h102.4.2	Battery current deviation	normal	h109.5.1	Charger error	normal	ch_status.current	Current	-15.1A
h102.4.1	Battery undervoltage	normal	h109.5.0	Charger status	charging	ch_st_0	On/off	On
h102.4.0	Battery overvoltage	normal	h109.6-7	Remaining charging time	78min	ch_st_1	Power error	OK
h102.5.7	Vehicle disch compatibility	compatible				ch_st_7	Over temperature	OK
h102.5.4	Normal stop before charging	no request				ch_st_10	Mode	discharging
h102.5.3	Vehicle status	contactor closed	h118.0.0	Dynamic control	compatible	ismon_iso_7	Isolation R	124kOhm
h102.5.2	Charging system error	normal	h208.0	Present discharge current	-10A	ismon_dc.voltage	DC voltage	384.7V
h102.5.1	Vehicle shift position	parking	h208.1-2	Available input voltage	50V	ismon_debug_v1	debug V1	201.9V
h102.5.0	Vehicle shift position enabled	enabled	h208.3	Available input current	09A	ismon_debug_v2	debug V2	156.2V
h102.6	State of charge	85%	h208.6-7	Lower threshold voltage	250V	ismon_status_0	Isolation safety	Safe
			h209.0	V2H charge/discharge spec	2	ismon_status_1	Selftest status	Passed
			h209.1-2	Approximate discharge time	0min	ismon_status_2	Rip calculation	OK
						ismon_status_3	Vdc status	>50V
						ismon_status_4	Command status	idle

Metering data		
ID	Description	Data
metering_0	L1 voltage	236.20V
metering_1	L2 voltage	234.70V
metering_2	L3 voltage	235.80V
metering_3	L1 current	-5.850A
metering_4	L2 current	-5.850A
metering_5	L3 current	-5.780A
metering_6	L1 active power	-1229.260kW
metering_7	L2 active power	-1224.520kW
metering_8	L3 active power	-1225.950kW
metering_9	Total active power	-3679.000kW
metering_10	L1 reactive power	-502.740kW
metering_11	L2 reactive power	-614.920kW
metering_12	L3 reactive power	-585.040kW
metering_13	Total reactive power	-1702.700kW

Figure 39

Charging and discharging of the Nissan Leaf V2G car is made possible through the OCPP TxProfile. At a positive “limit” the car battery is charged. With the entry of a negative number, the battery discharges. Several meter values, among which State of Charge, are successfully send out through OCPP.

```

1  [
2
3  "2dd8ea2c-82ce-4b5a-8ff0-c0c3929d1952",
4  "SetChargingProfile",
5  {
6
7    "connectorId": 1,
8    "csChargingProfiles": {
9      "chargingProfileId": 575,
10     "stackLevel": 0,
11     "chargingProfilePurpose": "TxProfile",
12     "chargingProfileKind": "Absolute",
13     "chargingSchedule": {
14       "startSchedule": "2019-03-18T13:44:01Z",
15       "chargingRateUnit": "A",
16       "chargingSchedulePeriod": [
17         {
18           "startPeriod": 0,
19           "limit": -15
20         }
21       ]
22     }
23   }
24 ]
25

```

Figure 40: Example of the charging profile set to discharge the battery at a current of 15A

Figure 41: Test run of a session performing charging and discharging alternately.

Several car and charger specific characteristics were noted at the first tests:

- 1 The car does not have any indicators to show charging or discharging. There is also no indicator for charging/discharging speed. The only indicator present shows the amount of time needed to finalise charging, with an accuracy of 59 minutes.
- 2 The discharge speed depends on the current SOC of the car and decreases when the SOC is lower. The difference is not yet specified in detail but is significant, with several hundreds of Watts difference being measured.
- 3 The Nissan Leaf allows discharging until 10% SOC.
- 4 When SOC reaches the lower or upper limit (10% or 100%) the charging/discharging sessions stops and cannot be restarted without driver interference (driving back and forth). This is default CHAdeMO behaviour which needs to be incorporated in steering protocols to allow continuous V2G sessions.
- 5 Sessions lasting over 24 hours are automatically stopped, which is normal behaviour for a regular charger but not desirable for a V2G charger. This is reported to the charge point manufacturer to be fixed.
- 6 The standby power usage of the charger is -600 a -700VAr (reactive) and 8W (active) power.

3.5.7 Experiment results

Situation:

Charging laboratory at Elaad office parking lot– 40 regular EV chargers, 1 V2G charger with a Nissan Leaf and 1 stationary battery.

- Regular chargers are in operation during office hours
- V2G charger in operation at variable times, including weekends

Elaad Office Energy management – The building consumes energy mostly on weekdays between 4:30 and 20:30. Only baseload usage in the weekends.

The Nissan Leaf has known arrival- and departure times, registered in Outlook. We wrote a program that translates the scheduled appointments of the car to setpoint SOC's for the car and battery.

We tested two use cases for INVADE.

Use case 1: V2G shared car vs V2G lease car

The Nissan Leaf uses the V2G charger for small trips during the day (= departure and return during an office workday). Car will be 100% charged upon departure and returns with unknown SOC. Charge/discharge transactions are supporting the predicted consumption of the building (= charging stays under the maximum profile, similar to how charging works in the Large-Scale public pilot).

The stationary battery is used as if it is actually a number of V2G cars operated as leased vehicles, arriving between 8 and 9 am with around 30-50% SOC and leaving between 17:00 and 18:00 pm with 100% SOC.

Hypothesis: The V2G Shared car has more added value for supporting the grid than the leased V2G car (simulated by the battery)

Use case 2: V2G Lease vs Battery

The Nissan Leaf is present at the charger following a leased car pattern (meaning it arrives in the morning and only leaves again at the end of the working day). A prerequisite is that the car needs to have 100% SOC at departure. Arrival SOC is variable. The charging and discharging of the battery support the predicted load on the parking premises.

As a counterpart of the V2G car, the stationary battery is operated as a battery: It is 100% full at the start of the working day, is gradually discharged to reduce load on the parking premises and is charged again at night.

Hypothesis: A stationary battery has more added value for supporting the grid than a leased V2G car.

3.5.8 Results

We coupled our V2G charging and battery operation to the Outlook agenda of our Nissan Leaf in order to operate the correct use case according to the predicted availability of the car.

First, we operated the stationary battery and the V2G charger separately to distinguish the profiles of both. It is clear that both batteries can start charging or discharging very rapidly, resulting in vertical lines in the curves.

Figure 42

In the following graph, we tested the communication between V2G charger and battery by charging the car through the battery and vice versa. It was herewith shown that the two types of flexibility respond to each other as desired.

Figure 43

Figure 44

Figure 41: The Outlook reservations for the week of which the test results are listed in this paragraph.

We operated both use cases simultaneously, based on the Outlook agenda reservations for the Nissan Leaf (figure 39 for the reservations that formed the basis of the following results).

For both use case 1 and 2, we obtained results that show the cooperation between the stationary battery and the V2G charger. In the experiment results below, we chose not to allow charging or discharging above 3.5 kW based on an advice from the manufacturer. Even at this low power output, the impact of the discharge on the operation of the battery can be seen: the battery discharge has a much more smoothed out start and finish, which indicates it only supplies the peak of the energy demand of the charging taking place in the mornings.

The following graph shows both cases occurring in one week. Use case 1 behaviour can be seen at May 13th, where the car arrived at the office site in the morning, after a weekend away. It was used with its (unknown) arrival SOC to help the energy management system of the building. At 14:00h, the car was reserved for a new drive (use case 2). This reservation was done after the time check programmed in the charger, so the battery was not full. This drive was booked to return the following day at 12:00h, so too late to help the energy management system. So, on May 14th, the stationary battery was the only flexibility available. For this reason, the battery recharged during the night to be fully prepared in the morning. On May 15th, the car was unexpectedly moved away from the charger. Again, a reservation occurred (use case 2) after our time check

was carried out. Fortunately for the driver, the car had just started discharging. A departure a few hours later would have resulted in an unsatisfying experience for the driver.

Figure 45

On May 16th, the use case 1 scenario could be carried out in the morning, but there was a scheduled drive (use case 2) at 15:30 so the car responded by charging immediately after the discharge support, to supply the car with sufficient SOC.

3.5.9 Conclusion

We are able to include V2G in the charging commands of a group of EV chargers and the discharge option can be of assistance to the strain on the local grid. However, this is mostly the case when the car follows a typical leased car pattern, i.e. it arrives in the morning and leaves at the end of the afternoon.

The shared car behaviour results in loss of days in which V2G can be executed. Throughout the tests, we noticed that a shared car operating under V2G suffers from the unpredictability of the drive reservations. Even though we had supplied all possible drivers with information about the procedure at hand and the possible consequences for their reservation, we experienced multiple late-notice reservations. We also experienced reservations in which the car was returned too late to be of assistance to the local grid.

With respect to the performance of the stationary battery compared to the V2G car, we succeeded in operating the two simultaneously. The leased car had enough battery in the morning to assist the charging, but the battery was still needed.

In conclusion, our use case 1 hypotheses were false: a leased car is the preferred V2G car.

The conclusion on the hypothesis for use case 2 depends strongly on the amount of leased V2G cars present. Only one car will not be of significant impact, but even after driving to work or home, the electric cars have enough remaining SOC to be of assistance. Therefore, if a company or neighbourhood has a high predictability of available V2G cars, the cars can help to reduce the morning and evening peak, even if they just arrive from a drive at the time they are needed.

Specific KPI's

3.6 Test: Share of renewable energy

3.6.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the smart charging algorithm on the amount of renewable energy that is used in EV-charging. Using the optimizing algorithms as designed in this Project, the optimal capacity is calculated based on historical energy consumption and renewable energy production data. Using this data, the algorithm predicts what the consumption and production will be in the near future and calculate an optimal capacity.

This algorithm was based around two optimization parameters, the share of renewable energy and the energy price. Since the test steps are analogue to all KPI's and the test results are based on the same optimization, both KPIs were calculated on the same dataset.

3.6.2 Test steps

Table 17. Test steps for KPIs

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Connect and configure assets to the IIP		OK
2	Collect baseline measurement data on building energy consumption	Reliable baseline data for comparison with smart charging data	OK
3	Renewable energy production data is sent to the IIP		OK
4	Spot price data is sent to the IIP		OK
5	Weather data is sent to the IIP		OK

6	This data is used to optimize the EV-charging capacity		OK
7	Collect results of the optimization algorithm	Reliable smart charging data for comparison with baseline measurement data	OK
8	Compare baseline measurement data with smart charging data	Reliable comparison between baseline and smart charging data for a sufficient period of time	OK

3.6.3 Baseline (quantified)

Figure 46. Baseline measurements for KPI 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3

Figure 47. Net energy consumption profile

3.6.4 Target value (with threshold)

The KPI ‘share of renewable energy’ is defined as the amount of energy that is used for electric vehicle charging instead of being (re)delivered to the grid. Or in formula:

$$\text{Share of renewable energy} = \frac{\text{Renewable energy produced} - \text{Renewable energy redelivered}}{\text{Renewable energy produced}}$$

3.6.5 Results

Figure 48. Results of optimization

Table 18: Share of renewable energy before and after optimisation

Day	Share of renewable energy		
	Before optimization	After optimisation	Difference
Monday	93%	98%	+ 5%
Tuesday	97%	97%	+ 3%
Wednesday	89%	93%	+ 4%
Thursday	98%	99%	+/-
Friday	77%	98%	+23%
Saturday*			
Sunday*			

*not taken into account because it is an office location and there is no electric vehicle charging in the weekends

3.6.6 Conclusion

It can be seen from the results that after optimization, done via the INVADE platform, the share of renewable energy that was effectively used increased dramatically. This was

shown to be a very effective way of managing surplus renewable energy production when consumption and production don't happen simultaneously.

3.7 Test: KW-max for grid connection

3.7.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values (to be updated)

3.7.2 Baseline (quantified)

For the Invade project the existing charging network of EVnetNL is made available for smart charging tests. This charging network consists of 800 charge stations located across the Netherlands in about 200 municipalities. All charge stations have a 3X35A Grid connection. The charge stations are from a handful of different suppliers and all support OCPP1.6.

Figure 49: Charging points in NL

Figure 50: Different charging point models

For the Dutch pilot sites, there are existing operating systems from Elaad and GreenFlux. The Dutch pilot takes into account all the national and international regulations, but also makes use of open standard protocols like OCPP and OSCP. The INVADE pilot also contributed to these protocols as an update of the OSCP protocol is developed under protocol name: OCMP. This should become the next OSCP version when the INVADE pilot tests prove the added value, which is currently being tested.

For more details about the practical set-up and the protocols used we refer to deliverable 10.4 and its addenda.

Customers were not informed of the INVADE program or the possible adjustment of their charging session. No complaints about charger performance were received during the pilot runtime, which is in line with the results we present in this chapter.

The smart charging can be viewed live at <https://www.prod.elaad.io/8091>.

Figure 51

The screenshot shows the 'Logging' tab of the INVADE web interface for station 'Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)'. It displays a table of charging session logs. The table has five columns: Time, Algorithm, Trigger, Optimized local grid limit, and Area. The logs show a series of charging sessions starting and stopping at various times, with the 'Optimized local grid limit' fluctuating between 895 A and 908 A. The 'Area' for all sessions is 'Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)'. Logos for Elaad, INVADE, and the European Union are visible at the bottom.

Time	Algorithm	Trigger	Optimized local grid limit	Area
15-8-2019 14:17:39	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	908 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:17:26	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	908 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:17:05	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	908 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:17:03	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	908 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:16:45	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	908 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:16:13	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	908 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:15:14	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	908 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:14:00	EqualAmpsPerSession	Comply to profile (DSO)	908 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:13:32	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:13:22	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:11:21	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:09:49	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:09:44	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:09:08	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:09:07	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:09:00	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:08:51	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:08:50	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:06:32	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:05:45	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:05:42	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)
15-8-2019 14:03:59	EqualAmpsPerSession	Charging start/stop	895 A	Arnhem (Schuytgraaf)

Figure 52

3.7.3 Reached value

In 2019, there were over 130.000 charging sessions on the stations in this pilot. Of these charging sessions 63.558 were limited to less that 20A of charging current at some point during the session. The connection times of the sessions that were impacted were around 40.2 minutes longer, which indicates that these sessions were not quite similar.

Table 19

Month	Non-impacted	Impacted	Total
Jan	5717	9098	14815
Feb	3201	10481	13682
Mar	5101	10227	15328
Apr	4854	10528	15382
May	10099	5007	15106
Jun	9774	4665	14439
Jul	11041	3283	14324
Aug	10089	4451	14540
Sep	6864	5818	12682
Oct			0
Nov			0
Dec			0
Total	66740	63558	130298

Figure 53

Figure 54

The DSO limits were lower in winter, which is why a larger share of charging sessions were impacted than during the summer period. In February 77% of charging sessions were limited, compared to 23% in July.

3.7.4 Conclusion

We have successfully limited charging sessions to comply with DSO constraints. The system is robust and can handle large numbers of sessions, responding to both changes within the charging sessions and changes in the profile settings accurately. The response time of the chargers to changes in setpoint is within minutes, resulting in the majority of sessions following the adjusted profile at the moment the next meter values are sent out by the chargers.

3.8 Test: APX price effects

3.8.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the prosumer optimization on the average energy price, as well as the differences in the total electricity bill. In this case, the end user is the owner of the building. In order to calculate this KPI, APX spot price data was collected on a fifteen-minute basis. The baseline as shown in 3.3.3 was combined with the baseline provided in 3.1.1. in order to calculate this.

3.8.2 Baseline (quantified)

Figure 55. APX spot price measurements

The average spot price for the baseline is € 0,04223 / kWh (€ 42,23 / MWh)

3.8.3 Target value (with threshold)

The target value for this KPI is below € 0,04223

3.8.4 Reached value

The reached value was € 0,04256 / kWh (€ 42,56 / MWh). This is slightly higher than the value for the baseline.

3.8.5 Conclusion

The reached value is slightly higher than the value found in the baseline, however there is only a minor difference (~0,5%). This is probably not a significant difference to base any major conclusions on. However, it should be noted that the share of renewable energy was

3.9 Test: Session duration

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the smart charging algorithm on the duration of the session.

Table 20: Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

	Expected result	Result
Collect baseline measurement data on session duration	Reliable baseline data for comparison with smart charging data	We do not know the arrival SOC of the EV's, nor can we be sure the cars are always 100% full when they leave the charger. Therefore, we use average charging duration. We have differentiated between total average duration and the difference between Smart Charged and baseline sessions.
Collect smart charging data on session duration	Reliable smart charging data for comparison with baseline measurement data	We performed smart charging based on DSO profiles for 1 year. Every 15 minutes the charging profiles are updated, if the bandwidth is at its upper limit. During each 15minute period, recalculated profiles are also generated when sessions are ended or added. On average this resulted in recalculated profiles every 30 seconds in the INVADE Platform. We were able to correct actual charging to stay within the boundaries, with only minimal exceptions.
Compare baseline measurement data with smart charging data	Reliable comparison between baseline and smart charging data for a sufficient period of time	Success, but only with DSO profile. There is no reason to suspect the smart charging algorithm would stop to function after the inclusion of a commercial profile.

3.9.1 Baseline (quantified)

When looking into the sessions with respect to the arrival time of the car (i.e. the moment at which the car is connected to the grid), we can distinguish a clear DSO profile in the distribution of impacted and non-impacted sessions. In the graph below, all 130.000 sessions charged within the project period January-September 2019 are listed.

Figure 56

The impact of smart charging on the ratio between charging time and connection time is likely highest for sessions that start between 10:00 am and 15:00 am, as these sessions generally stay connected for shorter time periods than sessions that start charging outside of this timeframe. This is visualized in the following graph. Any impact ordered through the INVADE algorithms on charging power will cause the lines for connection and charging time to move closer together in this group.

Figure 57

When looking in more detail into the sessions, the actual impact of smart charging on charging duration can be determined. In order to do this, a session outside of the timeframe described above is most likely to yield results, as the sessions with shorter connection times are more likely to be cut off before charging is finished, making analysis impossible. We will discuss these cut-off sessions further in the following paragraph.

Out of the sessions starting between 18:00 and 19:00, around 60% were impacted at some point during the charging session.

Figure 58

As can be seen, the connection time of the two groups was, on average, practically similar. The impacted sessions in this group were charging significantly longer than the non-impacted sessions, which is the expected effect of the smart charging algorithm applied. Because of the long connection time on average, it is unlikely the drivers noticed this. This analysis clearly demonstrates the flexibility available in charging sessions with sufficiently long connection times.

3.9.2 Reached value

The reduced charging rate can lead to more vehicles being cut off before they are fully charged, compared to the standard situation. We investigated whether this was the case, to get insight in the way in which EV drivers were likely to notice Smart Charging taking place.

We found that the impacted sessions were in fact not cut off more often than the sessions that were not impacted by the rate limits; 45% vs 49%, respectively. An explanation might be that the strongest reduction was applied to sessions that were connected the longest -- those starting at the end of the workday and lasted until the next morning -- and therefore had the most time to make up for the lowered speed.

Figure 59

As stated, before in paragraph 3.2, the impacted sessions were connected around 40 minutes longer, on average, than the non-impacted sessions, which makes a comparison of the effect on cut-offs a bit more complex than expected.

Comparison of the connection times between the sessions was already shown above, in which all sessions are plotted against the time the session started. Sessions that started around 17:00 and 18:00 were more likely to be impacted and that median charging time was almost similar to the connection time for sessions that started between 10:00 and 15:00h, which identifies these sessions as mostly “opportunity charging”. In these sessions, a higher amount of cut-off sessions (in which charging was ongoing now the session was ended by the driver) was observed than for the other starting times.

To find more sessions in which the EV drivers were likely to notice Smart Charging, we further analysed these cut-off sessions, comparing the amount of energy charged in the impacted and non-impacted cut-off sessions. In contrast to our expectations, in this group the sessions that were impacted charged more kWh than those that were charging at full speed throughout the connection time.

Figure 60

Even comparing sessions that started in the same hour, like we did in the previous comparison, shows the same result, with the impacted sessions charging more kWh for both non cut-off and cut-off sessions. An explanation is difficult to give without knowing more characteristics of the sessions, such as arrival SOC and battery capacity.

Figure 61

In all sessions described so far, only DSO limits were applied. These limits were derived from the maximum transformer capacity in the neighbourhoods in which the chargers

were virtually placed, combined with the power usage of the households. In order to prevent losing connection to the sessions or impacting the session of the EV driver to an extent that would lead to complaints, we never allowed a charging speed below 13A, even when the grid limits demanded this. During the pilot period, our sessions exceeded grid capacity limits in the winter months, as shown in the following figure. This shows that our virtual arrangement of chargers per transformer is, as calculated prior to the pilot, a challenging arrangement in which grid limitations are likely to be an obstacle during large scale adoption of electric vehicles. Especially during the winter months, in which more electricity is consumed through regular household usage, our current safety limit of 13A is not enough to maintain the grid once the actual coverage of EV that we have now simulated in INVADE is reached.

Figure 62

Figure 63

This result indicates a stronger intervention in charging sessions can be needed during certain moments of the year and/or day. Given the differences between charging needs we found, both with respect to connection times and battery State of Charge and capacity, we believe there is room for further adjustment once the characteristics of the sessions are known in more detail.

3.9.3 Conclusion

In order to prevent power quality issues or even power outages, more rigorous Smart Charging is needed, with further limitation of the amperage per session than we applied. To do this effectively, i.e. without causing a significant number of extra cut-off sessions or hindering the driving of the vehicle, the CPO and commercial aggregator need to have more detailed information on the ongoing charging sessions than is currently available. By knowing arrival SOC, type of battery (capacity and minimal accepted amperage) and in ideal cases also departure time, sessions can be scheduled in such a way that grid exceedance can be prevented. Since the currently obtained data show that the capacity problems are predominantly occurring in the sessions that are likely to be connected overnight, preventing grid overload seems possible.

4 Germany: Pilot in Freiburg

General KPIs

4.1 Test: Prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”

4.1.1 Purpose

To prove the benefits of using open standard protocols and reducing the possibilities of brand specific customizations. It's important to avoid local “tailor-made” solutions that will influence on the scalability, both in time and in re-structuring of register/database.

4.1.2 Abstract

In this subchapter the workflow is described adding new recipients of flexibility and new flexibility providers to the existing INVADE integrated platform (IIP). Today still some manual work is necessary. But even under these circumstances new parties can be added already today quite quickly. The outlook for the future is to provide an easy to handle app, new flexibility providers on household level are willing to use, and to enforce them to insert relevant device data by themselves. With an automatic data import into the IIP the timeframe for adapting new parties could be reduced nearly to zero. An upscaling of INVADE towards hundreds or even thousands of new customers would become very easily handlebar.

4.1.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

The following test steps are based on the actual status quo of the INVADE platform (without an app). The tests were conducted from the perspective of a flexibility operator using the platform as a software tool for providing flexibility services to a DSO.

With flexibility providers controllable households are meant. They consist of PV-generation systems as well as controllable loads like heat pumps, EV-chargers, household appliances and home storage systems. All these devices are controlled by a home management system which takes over the basic management role only overruled by IIP in certain times for providing services to the local DSO. Further the home management systems collect all necessary operational data and provides them for IIP via a cloud-platform solution. Finally, it is responsible for executing the control signals calculated by IIP on household level. In the German test site, we focused on the home

management system ‘Sunny Home Manager v2.0’ as well as the cloud-platform solution provided by the company SMA (Figure).

Figure 64: Sunny Home Manager 2.0

Since SMA is the market leader for solar hardware in Germany, badenova seeks a strong cooperation with this company. On the other hand, SMA already provides a widely used home management system, which is capable to make forecasts of PV-generation and load consumption and to calculate on this basis an operation scheme for the local controllable loads as well as battery. This system is furthermore capable to connect devices of different manufacturers. This is an important advantage as INVADE does not have to deal with a variety of proprietary communication standards of devices on house level. Instead INVADE can focus solely on connecting to the Sunny Home Manager as the lower energy management authority and this device deals with all local devices.

Main target of the system is to maximize self-sufficiency of the customer and in the same way to minimize the energy consumption from the grid, as the tariffs for residential customers are nearly three times as high as the production costs from the own PV-system. But: The optimization algorithm in the Sunny Home Manager focuses only on the local building. A connection to a superior optimization level was one of the main tasks in the INVADE project regarding the German test site. This connection was realized successfully and tested in real operation.

4.1.4 Test steps

Table21. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Add new recipient of flexibility	Flexibility customer established within 15min	Successful

2	Define contract between FO and flex recipient	Contract established within 10min	Successful
3	Check communication through open standards and protocols between recipient and FO according to contract defined	Recipient can execute and communicate instructions according to contracts (latency < 5 seconds)	Successful
4	Add new flexibility provider	Flexibility provider established within 10 min	Successful
5	Define contract between FO and flex provider	Contract established within 5-10 min. Master document in paper form is available	Successful
6	Check communication based open standards and protocols between flex provider and FO according to contract defined	FO is able to execute and communicate instructions according to contract (latency < 5 seconds)	Successful
7	Repeat steps 1-3 for 5 different randomly picked recipients	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	Successful
8	Repeat steps 4-6 for 10 flexibility providers	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	Successful

Definitions:

- Recipient of flexibility: Distribution System Operator (DSO)
- Flexibility provider: Household (with PV-generation as well as controllable loads like heat pumps, EV-chargers, household appliances and a home storage system)
- Flexibility operator: badenova AG & Co. KG
- Contract: Physical (future: electronic) document to be signed by agreement parties

4.1.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The KPI is measured in seconds, minutes, hours or days. Depending on the degree the procedure may be executed automatically.

4.1.6 Baseline (quantified)

As today the process for adding new parties in IIP is as follows:

- No. 1 of Table:
Here the new DSO (because 'recipient' is in our case the DSO) has to register in the IIP

- Therefore, it must create an account with filling certain given fields
- It has to define sub grids and zones, for which it wants to gather flexibility offers
- As bonus 'products' - means prices - have to be deposited to price the value of flexibility
- No. 2 of Table:
 - The contract must be signed between DSO and FO (badenova AG & Co. KG). A master document in paper form is available. So, the necessary time is quite short 5-10 min
- No. 4 of Table:
 - Because of the hierarchic data structure in IIP it takes some time to create a new flexibility provider (household in our case)

Figure 65: Hierarchic data structure in IIP

- Each asset must be created individually. The resources can become numerous, if PV-generation, heat pumps, EV chargers etc. are related to this asset (as it is in the badenova test site).

4.1.7 Target value (with threshold)

- Currently the INVADE API is used for creating the assets. We do not use the available 'AssetLoader'. This would be useful for the new creation of numerous assets in the future and would save a significant amount of time.

- The next step would be developing an app participating household automatically install. With accepting the 'terms of use' a contract with the FO could be closed automatically. The basic customer data could be transferred immediately to IIP and stored there.
- In the following the customer should be asked by the app to enter essential characteristics of his system by himself. This data could also be transferred to IIP automatically and stored there. This would significantly reduce the input time for new assets. All that was left would be to fill in gaps and check the entries made by the customer for plausibility.
- Basically, badenova's approach of switching the SMA platform between IIP and assets as middleware offers many advantages. If new flexibility providers are to be connected to IIP, it is not necessary to laboriously implement a communication path. Instead, the existing API interface of the SMA platform can be used. The SMA system handles all communication issues at household level. This approach saves already a lot of time.

4.1.8 **Reached value**

The times mentioned in Table could be met during testing.

4.1.9 **Conclusion**

Creating new recipients of flexibility or adding new flexibility providers can be done within minutes in the IIP today. The most time-consuming tasks are signing the physical contract and inserting all the relevant asset data. These tasks could be simplified very much in future, if an app would be developed, encouraging new flexibility provides to insert all relevant data by themselves. With this measurement even large numbers of new flexibility providers could be handled with more or less no additional work.

In general data transfer between flexibility providers and IIP is easily managed? and widely scalable as SMA is providing the data infrastructure for the households including distributed energy storages. The SMA home management system is capable of forecasting PV-generation and load consumption and to calculate on this basis an operation scheme for the local battery. This system is furthermore capable of connecting devices of different manufacturers. This is an important advantage as INVADE does not have to deal with a variety of proprietary communication standards of devices on the lower house level. Instead INVADE can focus solely on connecting to the SMA-cloud platform for collecting data as all Sunny Home Manager devices send relevant data to

this platform. So, it acts like a middle ware. An interface between the SMA cloud platform and INVADE has been programmed by badenova. It can deal with numerous households without restrictions. So – using this given interface – data processing is easy. On the way back to execute schedules calculated by INVADE specially developed gateways in the households are addressed via a common FTP-Server. Even here data processing is easy to handle. So, adapting new customers to the systems can be done very quickly.

4.2 Test: Demonstrate the improvements using batteries

4.2.1 Purpose

This is a comparative test. To demonstrate the improvement of using batteries due to better % usage, and at the same time reduce the probability of black-outs. Lower safety margin and maximum utilization in the installation to avoid power-peaks.

4.2.2 Abstract

KPIs proving the reduction of the vulnerability in latency by using batteries in households.

$$\text{KPI} = \text{actual response} / \text{theoretical response with "no" latency}$$

This implies that the response time for compensation of loss of power is measured and compared to a pilot requirement or theoretical standard.

4.2.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

As the German test site is a hybrid test site consisting of one large scale battery and several distributed PV-storages in private households, the test done was done with all devices. In the following the results for two households are shown exemplarily. The large-scale battery follows the IIP schedules exactly and with nearly no latency (ms-range).

The purpose of the installed home management systems on household level is to maximise self-sufficiency. Doing so, prosumers become highly unpredictable in terms of time and peak of fed-in power and consumed power. Exactly at this point, badenova and SMA want to create an additional benefit for the DSO as well as for the private customer by connecting the households to a superior entity (INVADE) and making the flexibility potential accessible to the DSO. The private household still optimizes its own consumption via the local Home Manager most time of the day and can offer auxiliary services to the DSO in dedicated time slots. This approach seems to be technically feasible, as many battery storages on household level are dimensioned too big and still

hold capacity-reserves, which are not used. The following Figure illustrates the approach.

Figure 66: Added value for private customers with home management system

4.2.4 Test steps

Table 22. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Send activation signal from FO. Start clock at point of activation.	Activation executed. Clock started.	Successful
2	Monitor the amp meter connected to the household. Record time to amp meter change- Record the response time and meter reading at activation.	Response time reading Amp meter reading	See Figure 69 and Figure
3	Compare with theoretical measure.	Ratio	See Figure 69 and Figure
4	Rerun test in the following manner: Simulating a black out.	Not done because home systems are not designed for islanding mode	
5	Disconnect power. Simulate black out	Not done because home systems are not designed for islanding mode	
6	Repeat steps 1-3	Done with several households. Response times and patterns remained stable	

4.2.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

As already described in other deliverables the basic business model for the German test site is peak shaving for the entire electrical grids in Freiburg – and Breisach (as both grids are not interconnected and therefore accounted separately). This requires an accurate load forecast by the DSO in order to identify the relevant hours with expected highest demands. badenova analysed historical data over several years and examined for all months and all days the hours with the highest expected peak loads.

4.2.6 Baseline (quantified)

In the following Figure 67 the load profile for the entire electrical grid in Freiburg is shown for the year 2017. This means the baseline as no peak shaving was undertaken. The highest peak over the whole year is accounted by a so called ‘peak tariff’. So, if the peak passes through due to an unprecise load forecast or technical problems controlling flexibility devices, all the financial advantage is lost. INVADE does not provide a load forecast for electrical grids. Therefore, it was the task of bn-NETZE in its role as DSO responsible for peak shaving from the perspective of the whole grid.

Figure 67: Load profile for entire electrical grid in Freiburg

4.2.7 Target value (with threshold)

The tests were conducted in September 2019. The following Figure68 shows the load forecast for this month. Load forecasts for all other months of the year were provided also. For this month highest peak load is expected on Thursdays in the hour between 10:00 and 11:00 a.m. So, tests have been conducted at this time to reduce cost effective peak load demand (Table 23).

Mittelwert von Bezug vorgelagertes Netz	Wochentag							Gesamtergebnis	Monat
Uhrzeit (Stunde)	Montag	Dienstag	Mittwoch	Donnerstag	Freitag	Samstag	Sonntag		
0	102310	107718	109615	110758	111130	109134	105155	108118	1
1	95588	101348	102983	103810	103932	102046	98985	101358	2
2	92465	97498	98940	99760	100340	97676	94450	97418	3
3	92373	96415	97395	99413	99840	96038	93280	96496	4
4	94790	98410	99138	101800	101338	96090	93078	97867	5
5	101615	106200	107235	109533	107628	98520	93493	103435	6
6	121258	125430	127090	128738	126150	104448	95625	118185	7
7	142698	146668	147115	148895	145928	110764	97433	133823	8
8	155743	159803	159050	162363	157904	120450	102588	144998	9
9	159123	162980	163583	166768	161266	128086	104933	149186	10
10	160633	165980	165523	168158	160388	130678	106900	150803	11
11	158713	164720	164250	166556	159270	134092	108593	150605	12
12	156565	159668	161650	164760	156826	130260	105895	147653	
13	156283	158628	159108	163830	151570	126000	99540	144580	
14	151598	154938	158848	159255	146334	125742	94195	141190	
15	151333	153688	160135	154263	144314	129776	97510	141272	
16	148883	150880	161033	154135	142744	128886	100440	140654	
17	152805	152593	159005	154605	147186	131734	108665	143510	
18	156353	158133	161610	157730	151530	140864	122128	149526	
19	158990	161823	163425	160605	155094	145768	131058	153597	
20	157870	158240	159908	160205	152496	143514	136493	152364	
21	144713	145708	147858	147783	141218	133640	129500	141218	
22	133485	133975	136708	136553	131500	126944	123758	131671	
23	119253	120128	122488	122473	119474	116110	112323	118819	
Gesamtergebnis	136060	139232	141404	141774	136475	121136	106501	131598	

Figure68: Load forecast for entire electrical grid in Freiburg

Table 23. Relevant time slot for peak shaving in September

Time Slot	Command	Purpose
September, Thursday, 10–11 a.m.	Request to IIP to discharge batteries as much as possible	Reduce demand peaks in the whole electricity grid in the morning (peak shaving)
Remaining time	0 kW	Minimize consumption from the public grid to maximize self-sufficiency in households (original intended function of home management system)

4.2.8 Reached value

Shown is in Figure 69 and Figure the control signal calculated by IIP based on the individual characteristics of the participating devices in the household (blue) as well as the response from the household over all (orange). Further the SOC of the local home storage system is plotted (grey).

Figure 69: September 5th, 2019, Freiburg, DES03

Figure 70: September 3rd, 2019, Breisach, DES08

Despite of some fluctuations the both households follow more or less exactly the control command from IIP. There is no countable latency. So, the optimum is already reached.

4.2.9 Conclusion

The tests have demonstrated that it is possible to control our DES via centralized signals from IIP in a very accurate way. The results show that the central control of DES can support the balance of energy flows in grids. There was no countable time delay between control signal and execution.

Apart from this control override by INVADE it is the aim of the home management system to maximize consumption of self-produced PV-energy and in consequence minimize the use of energy delivered from the public grid. The effective work of this lower management level is shown in Figure 69 and Figure also as outside the control window from 10:00-11:00 a.m. the grid supply of the households is reduced almost exactly to zero.

4.3 **Test: measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling by including a battery**

4.3.1 **Purpose**

This KPI will measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling by including a battery as part of an installation. This should be done at both for at household level, building level and on substation level.

4.3.2 **Abstract**

In the German test site, the large-scale battery is designed as multi-purpose device. First way of use is for peak shaving regarding the entire electrical grid in Freiburg. Second way of use is for local voltage control. Reason for this is in the selected case a farmer's house located at the end of a feeder. The property is equipped with four PV plants with a total installed power of 30.5 kWp. All four PV plants are connected via one single grid connection point to the public low voltage grid. The distance between the next substation and the end of the feeder is nearly 840 m. On the substation other feeders with PV generation are connected. Overall, an installed PV power of 331,8 kWp is connected to this point. On sunny days this already results in a voltage increase here. This effect is intensified towards the end of the long feeder due to the energy feed in of the PV-systems on the farmer's house. In fact, voltage limits at its grid connection point are violated by the local generation of electricity several times over the year. So, a further extension of the existing PV systems is not possible even if there is more than enough free space left on the barn's roof.

The voltage on the grid connection point of the farmer's house can rise up nearly 7.5% above the regular level on a day with maximum generation from the PV-Systems and regular load. Due to the geographical distance of the PV installations on the roofs to the grid connection point of the farmer's house the voltage increases further along the electrical line running on the property. Thus, there are occurrences where the acceptable voltage tolerance level of 10% at the connection point of the inverters is exceeded. In such cases the inverters shut down automatically and the PV-systems are no longer able to generate electricity. In consequence, the PV-system owner loses the guaranteed feed-in tariff for the not produced energy and demands compensation for lost revenues from the grid operator. Hence, a strong interest on both sides exists, that this event is avoided.

By using a large-scale battery located nearby the farmer's house the PV plant will be able to fully feed-in into the local distribution grid even during peak production periods.

The energy is foreseen not to be transported over the weak line immediately but to be stored within the battery temporarily. During night-time, this energy shall be transported without causing any problems over the low stressed line. The battery will work as a grid-friendly component exclusively operated by the local DSO. In addition, the DSO uses the CES as a supplement to the distributed storages as a means of peak-shaving device for the entire grid, if the battery is not required for its initial purpose. badenova follows here a multipurpose strategy for the CES.

4.3.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

The battery management system decides locally, if the battery should charge or discharge or just stay idle for the first goal of the CES – ensuring entire feeding-in of the PV plants and maintaining the voltage on an appropriate level. The necessary reaction time lays within a ms-range. So, it obvious, that this voltage control has to be executed locally without using the INVADE platform. The time needed to transfer voltage measurement data to IIP in Norway, calculate new operating schemes for the battery there and transmitting the schedules back for execution would take seconds. That is much so slow for an effective voltage control.

In many countries maximum and minimum voltage levels are given by law or standard:

- As per German standard VDE-AR-N 4105 voltage limits for distributed generation devices are set at $\pm 3\%$ to the initial voltage of the low voltage network. This limit is set lower than the tolerance band given by EN50160 as many RES in long feeders may add and at the end of the cable the voltage can get too high.
- Specified by European Standard EN50160 the voltage in house installations must vary only within tolerable limits of 230V $\pm 10\%$. Appliances in household must operate within this voltage range. If voltage limits are violated, it may occur that connected PV plants cannot feed-in. Once connected to the grid, the DSO has to enable a non-interruptible possibility to feed-in the generated electricity within the given regulatory framework.

4.3.4 Test steps

Table 24. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Identify day expecting significant voltage increases due to high PV-generation and low load (e.g. sunny Sunday afternoon).	Day identified	Successful

2	Track activation of automatic local voltage control using online monitoring.	Online monitoring enabled	See figure 68
3	Local voltage control is activated, if on one of the three phases a preset trigger level is exceeded.	Algorithm started	See figure 68
4	Track, if local voltage control is able to reach the preselected target value, which is lower than 230V+3%.	Voltage decreases and reach target value	See figure 68
5	Track, how much energy flow from the battery is needed to keep the preselected target value over the time.	Tracking enabled	See figure 68

4.3.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

See table.

4.3.6 Baseline (quantified)

The following Figure shows measurement data in the relevant feeder during a sunny period in August 2018 - before the CES was installed. Additionally, a theoretical calculation was done, taking into account the installed battery capacity until a minimum level of 30% for local voltage control. The theoretically possible effect on voltage is plotted in blue.

Figure 71: Measured voltage and calculated control potential of CES

For the CES we must also consider usages due to voltage control. Based on historical data, we expect an annual usage rate of about 3,000 interventions on quarter-hour basis. That corresponds to 8.55% of all quarter-hour intervals of a year.

4.3.7 Target value (with threshold)

If one of the phases L1, L2 or L3 exceeds a voltage level of 234V (trigger level), the CES will charge with a flexible adaptive charging power of max. 20 kW until the voltage drops to 232V or lower. The stored energy gets fed back into the grid during night.

4.3.8 Reached value

The following Figure shows the first results from the regular operation of local voltage control.

Figure 72: Results from operation local voltage control

It can be seen, that the algorithm works. Immediately, when the trigger level of 234 V is reached in one phase it is activated and charges the battery. So, the charging power is a mirror of the voltage but running always a little bit in behind. 10 kW mean 4V voltage reduction. But: Some voltage peaks are not cut completely because control speed of local voltage control is not fast enough. This is a quite common situation on sunny days with some clouds. If a cloud darkens the sun the PV generation is reduced within ms and connected to that the voltage in the feeder. The same occurs vice versa if the cloud passes away. Then the generation increases with very sharp ramps and in consequence the voltage in the local grid. To handle this situation a revised voltage control software was developed and uploaded on the battery management system. By the time of writing this report measurement results were not yet available.

4.3.9 Conclusion

This case is an excellent example of how a battery storage device can help to secure full generation of renewable energies without expensive grid enforcement. At the same time, new potentials for expanding existing PV-plants on the roofs with more panels connected to the unchanged weak feeder, can be tapped. The pilot also proves that a battery can serve two separate use cases and value streams – local voltage control combined with peak shaving for the entire grid. It has been shown, that the battery reduces over voltages significantly.

Specific KPIs

4.4 Test: DSO Cost Savings

This is not really a test but an analytic comparison of different solutions for the same problem in the same weak grid area (grid reinforcement vs. battery). The challenge is to avoid over voltages there due to a high share of renewable energy generation.

4.4.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

To calculate the cost savings for the DSO we compare the costs for conventional grid reinforcement with the investment costs in a battery.

4.4.2 Baseline (quantified)

A conventional grid reinforcement would have cost about 123,000€ according to an internal cost calculation. The main cost factors are for civil engineering. Further a local road has to be crossed underground:

Cable length

- 810 m cable system NAVY 4x150 - double cable
- 30 m cable system NAVY 4x150 - single cable

Civil engineering

- 1/3 fortified – 280 m
- 2/3 unfortified – 560 m

Cost factors

- 160€/m fortified double cable system
- 100€/m unfortified double cable system
- 140€/m fortified single cable system
- 80€/m unfortified single cable system
- 3,000€ for cable distribution installation incl. civil engineering
- 20,000€ for passing under local road

So total cost for grid reinforcement would had been: 123,200€.

4.4.3 Target value (with threshold)

By using a large-scale battery located nearby the farmer's house the PV plant will be able to fully feed-in into the local distribution grid even during peak production periods.

The energy is foreseen not to be transported over the weak line immediately but to be stored within the battery temporarily. During night time, this energy shall be transported without causing any problems over the low stressed line. The battery will work as a grid-friendly component exclusively operated by the local DSO. Grid reinforcement can be avoided.

4.4.4 Reached value

In total, purchase and installation of the CES has cost about 129,000€.

4.4.5 Conclusion

As it is today grid reinforcement (€ 123,000) would have been slightly cheaper than a battery (€ 129,000). But: With the CES it is possible to create additional revenues by contributing to peak shaving. Further battery prizes are expected to fall over the next years. So, in a short period the battery solution is expected to be even cheaper compared to grid reinforcement.

4.5 Test: Additional DSO cost savings

4.5.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The aim is cost saving regarding the peak power fees for the entire grid of 'bn-NETZE' to the upstream grid operator. This is not really a test but an analytic calculation, what cost savings were possible, if storages in different numbers would have been operated in an optimized way.

4.5.2 Baseline (quantified)

In addition to savings by avoiding grid reinforcement the DSO can use installed batteries to reduce peak power fees. The price for peak power is given by the upstream grid operator, which is in case of 'bn-NETZE' the grid operator 'Netze BW'.

For now, 10 DES are interconnected in private households in the German testsite, but not all of them are connected to the same grid. In addition to the small batteries comes one large CES. Depending on the voltage level at the connecting substations, different prices are relevant. For the whole electricity grid in Freiburg, Netze BW asks for 90.77€ / kWa for the highest yearly peak. For the not connected sub grid in Breisach the costs are 92.68€ / kWa. Overall, the prices are between 90 and 115€ / kWa. The following

table shows the complete price overview for grid usage from the upstream grid operator 'Netze BW'.

Table 25. Grid usage tariffs from upstream grid operator 'Netze BW'

	Pricing system			
	Yearly use duration $T_m < 2.500$ h/a		Yearly use duration $r T_m > 2.500$ h/a	
Extraction point:	Peak price €/kWh	Aggregate price Cent/kWh	Peak price €/kWh	Aggregate price Cent/kWh
High voltage grid	11.00	3.41	90.77	Freiburg 0.22
Substation high & medium voltage	11.06	3.47	92.68	Breisach 0.20
Medium voltage grid	16.37	4.66	114.78	0.72
Substation medium & low voltage	17.14	4.66	115.53	0.72
Low voltage grid	18.02	4.76	101.82	1.41

→ The price table from the TSO results in a saving potential of $\approx 90\text{€}$ per controllable kWh

4.5.3 Target value (with threshold)

The potential power supply by one single battery depends on the battery capacity, structure of the energy demand in the household, maximal power performance of the inverter and the time range when the peak occurs. So far, we currently assume that DESs can provide about 1kWh of flexibility on average.

4.5.4 Reached value

The following Table and Table show the calculated cost saving potential in both grids 'Freiburg' and 'Breisach' in the scenarios a) 10 DES b) 100 DES and c) 1000 DES are interconnected and contributing to peak shaving. We separated three more sub cases i) 0,5 kW controllable power are available per device ii) 1 kW is available or iii) 2 kW are available. In all cases it is assumed, that the power can be delivered for one hour.

It can be seen in Table , that with 1 kWh of flexibility on average in the grid 'Freiburg' cost savings per year of 90.770€ are possible, if 1000 households contribute. In the grid of 'Breisach' the amount is slightly higher with 92.680€.

Table 26. Peak shaving cost saving potential 'Freiburg'

Saving Potential 'Freiburg' (90.77€ / kWa)		Number of installed batteries in the Grid		
		10	100	1000
Available Power per Battery for Peak Shaving	0.5 kW	454€	4,539€	45,385€
	1 kW	908€	9,077€	90,770€
	2 kW	1,815€	18,154€	181,540€

Table 27. Peak shaving cost saving potential 'Breisach'

Saving Potential 'Breisach' (92.68€ / kWa)		Number of installed batteries in the Grid		
		10	100	1000
Available Power per Battery for Peak Shaving	0.5 kW	463€	4,634€	46,340€
	1 kW	927€	9,268€	92,680€
	2 kW	1,854€	18,536€	185,360€

These are significant amounts. But on the other side a reimbursement must be payed to the contributing households for giving the control over their devices to the flexibility operator. So, the real cost savings would be significantly lower.

4.5.5 Conclusion

For the ten already installed DESs and one CES we do not expect high cost savings due to relatively low available controllable capacity compared to the total power peak in the grids. However, if we predict a rapid increase of controllable DES due to further market penetration a relevant cost saving potential is evident and can be made accessible by the INVADE platform.

4.6 Test: Additional revenues for private households

4.6.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

This is not really a test but an analytic calculation, what additional revenues for private households are necessary at least to convince them giving control over their devices to a flexibility operator.

4.6.2 Baseline (quantified)

Households must receive financial compensation so that they will provide their batteries for peak shaving. The compensation must be at least as high as the costs for the household by participating in this peak shaving model: Households lose energy from their batteries, which they have to cover later from the grid. Since self-produced electricity is cheaper than power purchase from the grid, the DSO has to compensate this difference. In addition, the DSO has to compensate the households due to additional charging cycles of the battery what correlates with a shorter lifetime of the battery. This mainly depends on the frequency of use of the batteries for a peak shaving model. At a relatively low usage frequency, this part of compensation could be negligible.

$$C_i \geq (P_B - P_E) * \sum_{t=1}^T (F_{ti}) + \beta * T$$

Compensation for household i (C_i) must be equal or higher than the difference between powers price for purchase and feeding in $(P_B - P_E)$ multiplied with the sum of all power provided as flexibility (F_{ti}), plus a depreciation factor of the battery multiplied with the amount of flexibility usages. Otherwise a household would not participate in this business model.

4.6.3 Target value (with threshold)

For now, we believe that DSOs should treat grid-friendly battery systems like other controllable electronic devices. According to the German Energy Act (§ 14a EnWG), DSOs are obliged to reduce grid usage costs for households with grid-friendly installation, but the amount of reduction, however, is not prescribed by law exactly. Even it is under discussion, if batteries are covered by the paragraph. So, a clarification would be very helpful.

4.6.4 Reached value

A comparison of the reduced grid usage prices between different DSOs in Germany has shown that for an average household with an annual remaining demand of 1,500 kWh (4,500 kWh in total, 3,000 kWh PV-production), the potential annual cost savings are between 24 and 91 EUR).

Table28. Potential annual cost savings due to grid friendly tariffs

DSO	Potential Annual Cost Savings for Average Household
Netze BW	91.04€
EWS	87.82€
Stadtwerk Kirchzarten	82.11€
Albwerk Netze	78.72€
Stadtwerke Lindau	74.49€
Stadtwerke Gammertingen	74.20€
Stadtwerke Konstanz	73.66€
Syna	69.62€
Stadtwerke Radolfzell	65.28€
ED Netze	58.91€
Netze Mittelbaden	53.73€
Stadtwerk Emmendingen	46.59€
Stadtwerk am See	36.95€
bnNetze	24.45€

4.6.5 Conclusion

The additional revenue for private household varies widely depending on the responsible DSO. For further development, we expect DSO to implement a more appropriate compensation scheme for network-friendly use of DSOs in private households. Therefore, a change within the regulatory framework would be very helpful.

4.7 Test: Frequency of flexibility usage

4.7.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

This is not really a test but an analytic calculation, home many control signals are necessary over one year to receive an optimal result in peak shaving.

4.7.2 Baseline (quantified)

The frequency of the flexibility usage depends on several factors. First at all, it depends on the structure of the peak loads in the grid. The more uniquely high the peaks are, the less flexibility usages are needed. In addition, the amount of installed batteries and their potential for flexibility supply important too. It is important to keep in mind that reducing one peak will produce new peaks in the following which must be reduced also. Or all the economic benefit will be lost. Please refer to Figure 67: Load profile for entire electrical grid in Freiburg.

4.7.3 Target value (with threshold)

The higher the desired peak reduction, the more peaks must be considered afterwards. Therefore, as in the cost saving calculation in subchapter 4.5.4, we have to determine the frequency under certain assumptions about the amount of installed batteries and average potential power supply by one battery.

4.7.4 Reached value

Table 29. Number of flexibility usage per controllable device in 'Freiburg'

Flexibility usage per year in 'Freiburg'		Amount of controllable batteries in the sub grid		
		10	100	1000
Controllable power per battery	0.5 kW	1 flexibility usage	1 flexibility usage	1 flexibility usage
	1 kW	1 flexibility usage	1 flexibility usage	1 flexibility usage
	2 kW	1 flexibility usage	1 flexibility usage	3 flexibility usage

Table 30. Number of flexibility usage per controllable device in 'Breisach'

Flexibility usage per year in 'Breisach'		Amount of controllable batteries in the sub grid		
		10	100	1000
Controllable power per battery	0.5 kW	1 flexibility usage	1 flexibility usage	8 flexibility usage
	1 kW	1 flexibility usage	1 flexibility usage	34 flexibility usage
	2 kW	1 flexibility usage	3 flexibility usage	349 flexibility usages

4.7.5 Conclusion

Since we could not run peak shaving tests for an entire year so far, we can just predict the frequency of flexibility usage from historical data. For the sub-grid Breisach we expect 1 – 349 and for Freiburg 1 – 3 flexibility usages, depending on the amount of installed batteries and supplied power from each device.

4.7.6 Test: Flexibility Potential of DES

Testing and examining the flexibility potential that DES can offer in addition to the actual purpose of optimizing self-consumption.

4.7.7 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

On 19th of February 2019 four scenarios were tested on five DESs in different grids. The responses were measured to examine to what extent the DESs have followed the implemented commands. The day before all five batteries had been fully charged.

4.7.8 Baseline (quantified)

For none of the scenarios we can define a baseline of how the energy flows would have proceeded without any intervention from outside the household, as we cannot replicate all exogenous variables such as weather, battery state of charge and household energy consumption. But: As it is the original intended function of the used home management system to optimize the self-consumption of produced PV-power without any external

control signal the energy exchange between the household and the grid can be most times expected at zero.

4.7.9 Target value (with threshold)

To control the house point energy flow control signals were sent. The commands were defined as follows (Table 31)

Table 31. Test schedule for testing customer response without former optimization calculation

Time Slot	Command	Purpose
8 – 9 a.m.	Feeding in 1 kW into the grid	Reduce demand peaks in the whole electricity grid in morning (peak shaving)
11 a.m. – 2 p.m.	Consumption of 2 kW from the grid	Avoiding feed in peaks in the whole electricity grid due to high PV penetration at noon
6 – 7 p.m.	Feeding in 1 kW into the grid	Reduce demand peaks in the whole electricity grid in the evening (peak shaving)
9 – 11 p.m.	Feeding in 1.5 kW into the grid	Grid support as response to a simulated power plant collapse
Remaining time	0 kW	Minimizing energy use from public grid (original intended function of home management system)

4.7.10 Reached value

The following 73 shows as an example the response of one household.

HouseInPoint (negative = feed-in, positive = grid-supply):

Figure 73: Response of one household without former optimising calculation by IIP

Shown is the control signal (dotted line) as well as the response from one household as example for all participating customers. It was a sunny day with high PV generation. Further the SOC of the local home storage system is shown. It explains, why the control

signal over noon could not be executed (storage was fully charged). Even it becomes clear, why grid support at night was only partly successful (storage was empty).

The following Table 32 shows the average response of all participating households.

Table 32. Average response of all contributing households

Time Slot	Command & Power Flow Direction	Average Response
8 - 9 a.m.	- 1 kW	- 0.82 kW
11 a.m. – 2 p.m.	+ 2 kW	- 1.38 kW
6 – 7 p.m.	- 1 kW	- 0.51 kW
9 – 11 p.m.	- 1.5 kW	- 0.73 kW

4.7.11 Conclusion

During the first scenario in the morning, the DESs performed close to the sent control signal. Charging the batteries, the day before could have a significant impact on this scenario. The second scenario at noon, the request was not fulfilled at all. Due to high PV production, the batteries were partially fully charged and could not absorb any further energy. Instead of charging the battery from the grid, the PV power had to be fed into the grid. In the last two scenarios, the requests were met about halfway.

This test shows, that without optimizing calculations by INVADE only an average response ratio of 0,51 to 0,82 can be expected. This means: If one kW is requested only a value between 0,51 to 0,82 is delivered in average. This proves the benefit of INVADE, as IIP calculates on all available operating data and device restrictions a realistic schedule which can be executed without problems by 100% (refer to sub chapter 4.2.8).

5 Bulgaria: Pilot in Albena

General KPIs

5.1 Test: Prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”

5.1.1 Purpose

To prove the benefits of using open standard protocols and reducing the possibilities of brand specific customizations. It’s important to avoid local “tailor-made” solutions that will influence on the scalability, both in time and in re-structuring of register/database. Applies to all use-cases.

The available API communication with the IIP is not (yet) an open standard protocol and thus no commercially available services exist to communicate with it. The only way Albena was able to communicate with the IIP was to create a custom message bridge, which would connect the IIP to both the battery and boiler systems. No other alternatives or suggestions were provided by the consortium or IIP developing partners.

5.1.2 Abstract

Standard defined methodology used to reduce time of adaptation in scaling up the pilots.

This KPI should prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”.

Because there is manual process involved in configuring a new site (scaling up), and there is also the consideration of the necessity for using a message bridge, it is practically impossible to reach “0” timeframe for adopting new customers.

5.1.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

Installation ready for test and supporting the test steps.

5.1.4 Test steps

Table 33. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Add new recipient of flexibility	Flexibility customer established within xx seconds	Added to the platform within ~ 10 min on average
2	Define contract between FO and flex recipient	Contract established within xx minutes	N/A
3	Check communication through open standards and protocols between recipient and FO according to contract defined	Recipient is able to execute and communicate instructions according to contracts (latency < xx seconds)	1 sec to 60 sec
4	Add new flexibility provider	Flexibility provider established within xx seconds	N/A
5	Define contract between FO and flex provider	Contract established within xx minutes	N/A
6	Check communication based open standards and protocols between flex provider and FO according to contract defined	FO is able to execute and communicate instructions according to contract (latency < xx seconds)	N/A

Albena is using the platform for self-optimization. Albena does not use external parties as flexibility operators and does not connect to e.g. a BRP using the platform.

5.1.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The precondition for adding a new customer (flexibility site) is that all hardware (including controllers, sensors and physical communication), and software equipment (controller software with the latest version) has been installed on the flexibility site. After the already mentioned precondition is met, the connection with the IIP is performed in two steps:

- Configure the IIP with the new site
- Configure the message bridge to pass messages from the IIP to the controller and vice versa

The test procedure consists of measuring the time it takes to perform the connection to the IIP for each of the above listed steps.

Once the communication test has been established, a latency data exchange test will be performed. Unfortunately, both Albena's SCADA and the internal software of the battery do not support high resolution historical data, so the test results will be measured manually. The test is focused on control signal latency and reaction of the customer's

sites (either battery or water heaters). The test will be performed at the installed battery and two hotels: Maritim Hotel Paradise Blue and Hotel Boryana.

5.1.6 Baseline (quantified)

No previous values exist. Baseline is defined based on experience with the project.

5.1.7 Target value (with threshold)

Considering there is manual work involved with configuring a new customer in the platform, it is both error prone and also depends on the user's knowledge of the system, we aim to complete configuring a new customer in the platform within 30minutes.

5.1.8 Reached value

The table below represents the time it takes to configure a new customer in the platform along with the message bridge to connect the receiving device. The difference in boiler installation time here is mainly because Hotel Boryana and Maritim Hotel Paradise Blue both have solar thermal collectors which requires more asset configurations.

Table 34. Time needed to configure assets

	Site location	Configuring in IIP	Configuring message bridge
1	Battery	6min	6min
2	Maritim Hotel Paradise Blue	6min	6min
3.	Hotel Boryana	6min	6min
4.	Hotel Nona	4min	4min
5.	Hotel Elitsa	4min	4min
6.	Hotel Sandy Beach	4min	4min
7.	Hotel Gergana	4min	4min

After the communication was established, the latency data exchange test was performed, and the latency distribution graph is presented below. 50 sample communication data exchange messages were tracked per each of the three sites and the reaction time was measured.

Figure 74

5.1.9 Conclusion

Several issues were discovered while performing the tests for this KPI:

- The KPI is unclear on the scope of the test. i.e., if adding new customers includes energy storage selection, ordering, transportation, installing, initial testing, configuring, etc, then the adoption time for new customers could very well go over a few months.
- The API of the IIP does not currently use available open standard protocols, and thus there are no commercially available solutions to communicate with it. The only possible way is to develop custom communication services, which inadvertently will be tailor-made.

Data exchange latency is also acceptable considering internal controller clock mismatches with the internal clock of the IIP. The very broad distribution of the battery should be bettered; however, this could be done at later stages as the custom communication message bridge between the IIP and the device is perfected. The longest observed latency is 60 seconds for reaction time, which represents a potential maximum state of charge deviation of 3.75kWh. This is acceptable given the circumstances. The late bringing up of the platform allowed for a smaller test window and thus smaller development reaction time from pilot sites.

5.2 Test: Demonstrate the improvements using batteries

5.2.1 Purpose

This is a comparative test. To demonstrate the improvement of using batteries due to better % usage, and at the same time reduce the probability of blackouts. Lower safety margin and maximum utilization in the installation to reduce power-peaks.

5.2.2 Abstract

KPIs proving the reduction of the vulnerability in latency by using batteries in households.

$KPI = \text{actual response} / \text{theoretical response with no latency}$

This implies that the response time for compensation of loss of power is measured and compared to a pilot requirement or theoretical standard.

However, in Bulgaria islanding mode must be permitted explicitly by the DSO. Such permission Albena does not have, therefore this test has not been performed.

Moreover, Flexibility Operator is not included in the scope of testing at the Albena site.

5.2.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

“Theoretical response” has been defined.

Amp meter connected to the battery.

5.2.4 Test steps

Table 35. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Send activation signal from FO. Start clock at point of activation.	Activation executed. Clock started.	OK
2	Monitor the amp meter connected to the battery. Record time to amp meter change- Record the response time and meter reading at activation.	Response time reading Amp meter reading	OK

3.	Compare with theoretical measure	Ratio	OK
4.	Rerun test in the following manner: Simulating a black out.	Run new tests after adjustments	N/A
5.	Disconnect power. Simulate black out		N/A
6.	Repeat steps 1-3		OK

5.2.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values.

Not applicable for Albena.

5.2.6 Baseline (quantified):

No previous values exist. Baseline is defined based on experience with the project.

5.2.7 Target value (with threshold):

No target value was specified because islanding mode is not permitted by the local DSO.

5.2.8 Reached value

None because of lack of permission by the local DSO.

5.2.9 Conclusion:

This test is not suitable for the allowed time in Albena due to the following reasons:

- The test requires for an FO to schedule and initiate an activation signal. At this point Albena AD employs only the automatic optimization of the IIP without an FO contract.
- Islanding mode is normally forbidden by the DSO in Bulgaria. Such permission was not issued also for the PV system that was installed.

Specific KPIs

5.3 Test: Cost savings from optimized energy flows

Since the beginning of 2019 Albena is on a flexible tariff contract with its energy supplier, which in Albena's case means that the price per consumed MWh can vary each hour. The price is formed using IBEX (Independent Bulgarian Energy Exchange) market's day-

ahead market energy price plus added a fixed cost for imbalances. To achieve real financial benefit from the adjusted power flows, Albena will shift energy demand from high-priced-hours on the day-ahead-market to lower-priced hours. This will be done as follows:

- Charge or discharge an installed 201kWh battery using automatic load profile generation algorithms provided by the IIP.
- Heat or not-heat water stored in boilers at 2 hotels using automatic load profile generation algorithms provided by the IIP.
- Heat or not-heat water stored in boilers at 4 hotels using a manually calculated predefined load profile curve.

5.3.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The resulting cost savings will be presented in percentage saved from the total cost paid per either boiler installation energy consumption or battery usage.

Test period ranges are as follows:

- Boilers: from 01.07.2019 until 30.09.2019
- Battery: from 10.09.2019 until 30.09.2019

Comparison is done as follows:

- Comparison between average cost per MWh for all of Albena against the measured and calculated average cost per MWh for each individual boiler installation or battery

Table 36

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Receive Market Data available	Hour prices	OK
2.	Reschedule power consumption for next day	New schedules for energy at low energy prices	OK
3.	After the day new evaluation required		OK
4.	Compare cost of energy to Albena cost for normal day	New prices	OK

5.3.2 Baseline (quantified)

Historical values are unavailable for comparison due to the following reasons:

- On 01.01.2019 Albena switched from a flat tariff with a fixed cost per MWh to a flexible tariff with variable cost per MWh
- Albena did not have individual consumption meter reading most boiler installations until summer season 2019

In this case reference values will be used by bringing in and analysing similar boiler installations, which do not optimize their energy flows.

5.3.3 Target value (with threshold)

Albena aims to have an average of at least 10% cost reduction in energy consumption due to optimized energy flows.

5.3.4 Reached value

Boilers

Table 37

July			
Hotel	Optimization type	Optimized average	Albena average
Elitsa	MANUAL	103.635 BGN	112.36 BGN (+8.42%)
Gergana	MANUAL	99.323 BGN	112.36 BGN (+13.13%)
Nona	MANUAL	94.377 BGN	112.36 BGN (+19.05%)
Sandy Beach	MANUAL	103.245 BGN	112.36 BGN (+8.83%)
Maritim Paradise Blue	NONE	106.858 BGN	112.36 BGN (+5.15%)
Boryana	NONE	102.267 BGN	112.36 BGN (+9.87%)

August			
Hotel	Optimization type	Optimized average	Albena average
Elitsa	MANUAL	101.561 BGN	109.47 BGN (+7.79%)
Gergana	MANUAL	100.899 BGN	109.47 BGN (+8.49%)
Nona	MANUAL	99.639 BGN	109.47 BGN (+9.87%)
Sandy Beach	MANUAL	101.654 BGN	109.47 BGN (+7.69%)
Maritim Paradise Blue	INVADE	96.571 BGN	109.47 BGN (+13.36%)
Boryana	INVADE	96.545 BGN	109.47 BGN (+13.39%)

September			
Hotel	Optimization type	Optimized average	Albena average
Elitsa	MANUAL	108.9 BGN	110.53 BGN (+1.5%)
Gergana	MANUAL	108.214 BGN	110.53 BGN (+2.14%)
Nona	MANUAL	107.535 BGN	110.53 BGN (+2.79%)
Sandy Beach	MANUAL	106.487 BGN	110.53 BGN (+3.8%)
Maritim Paradise Blue	INVADE	102.464 BGN	110.53 BGN (+7.87%)
Boryana	INVADE	105.472 BGN	110.53 BGN (+4.8%)

In this case reference values will be used by bringing in and analysing similar boiler installations, which do not optimize their energy flows.

5.3.5 Conclusion:

The results show significant cost reduction. As expected, in the most active months July and August the cost reduction reaches more than 13% because the used energy in this time period is high. The optimized power flows contribute to the increased consumption of low-priced energy while the peak-priced energy has been avoided.

5.4 Test: Cost savings from increased RES share

The volatility of RES generation is often the reason for power feed in the grid nowadays. As the feed in tariffs across Europe are decreasing, the fed in energy is considered as a loss for the owner of the installation. Batteries and controllable loads are thus seen as a solution to the problem as they may offer optimized consumption curve that is adapted to the RES generation. The increased RES share leads to cost savings from avoided grid energy costs.

Normally, when the energy is very cheap, an algorithm that doesn't consider the RES could send control signal that loads the boilers with hot water. Later, when also the sun generates hot water in the solar thermal stations, could possibly lead to over-heating and further infrastructure problems.

5.4.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The algorithms in the IIP predict not only the consumption, but also the RES generation. The evaluation considers the RES potential of the day and compare it to the actually utilized potential.

Therefore, the measurement will be based on the overall generated electrical energy that was

- Locally used at the consumer site
- Not generated due to grid limitations and/or lack of possibility to feed in to the grid

5.4.2 Baseline (quantified)

As the PV system has been installed within the duration of INVADE, there is no previous data to be compared with.

5.4.3 Target value (with threshold)

Main goal of the test is to show the benefits of a centralized energy storage that would store the excess energy from RES and then release it for local use. Therefore, target value is zero energy fed in to the grid and zero limitations set to the PV generation.

5.4.4 Reached value

The overall produced energy during September 2019 is 2781,47 kWh.

Not a single time the PV generation has been limited.

No energy has been fed into the middle voltage grid. All of the generated PV energy has been used locally.

5.4.5 Conclusion

The test shows that no losses have been detected during the test period.

The cost savings from increased RES share represent the whole amount of generated energy by the PV.

5.5 Test: % decreased max power

5.5.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The decreased max power is important KPI that represents the ability of the battery to assist the local low voltage network in peak times. In some cases, the used power by the consumers reaches so high values that threaten the stability of power supply because the high current flows could lead to circuit breaks by the transformer protection. In those cases, the battery operation in kWmax control is crucial for the stability of the grid.

The measurement takes place locally. The battery software allows to set an interval in which the battery will operate. In the Albena case max reached power is 800 kW which is below the 1000 kW capacity of the secondary substation. This means a stable operation of the transformer and no need to include battery. However, for test purposes we set the max consumed power by the transformer to 630 KW to simulate as if the transformer had less capacity.

5.5.2 Baseline (quantified)

No previous requests for transformer extension have been identified.

5.5.3 Target value (with threshold)

Target of the test is to keep up the power limits in all times during the test.

5.5.4 Reached value

Success: In all times the set max power limits have been kept.

5.5.5 Conclusion

The conclusion of the test is clear: Batteries can provide emergency power to the local low voltage grid and this way provide help in emergency peak times during which the maximum output power of the secondary substations has been reached.

Such peak times happen in rare cases. However, when shortage of the secondary substation is detected, the DSO or the microgrid operator is obliged to extend its max output power. The investments are significant. By operating a battery in the low voltage grid such investments can be avoided.

5.6 Test: Frequency of flexibility

In D10.5 this test has been described rather as a measure of the potential for providing services to third parties by offering flexibility. Therefore, the flexibility potential is seen in the context of Albena as a high-level industrial consumer.

5.6.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The flexibility requests are done manually. In order to keep the IIP general, it was decided not to create a direct connection the BRP. Therefore, whenever the BRP needs flexibility it could be done manually either electronically or by phone.

5.6.2 Baseline (quantified)

No historical flexibility requests have been received.

5.6.3 Target value (with threshold)

Target is at least once each 24 hours to receive and to respond to flexibility requests by the BRP.

5.6.4 Reached value

No interest by the BRP in flexibility provision during the tested period. Explanation is the low capacity of flexibility that has been offered and the short period of testing.

5.6.5 Conclusion

The lack of interest of the BRP shows that the capacity of offered flexibility was insufficient. The average peak power that Albena uses in high season is above 10 MW.

In this case the offered flexibility of the battery which is 200 kWh and by the boiler stations which is in most cases around 500 kWh should be extended to more controllable loads.

Further explanation for the lack of interest is the short period of testing. The tests will continue until the end of the project.

5.7 Test: Stick to a predefined load profile

5.7.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The IIP does not currently support predefined profile and does not plan to implement it by the end of the INVADE Horizon 2020 project. The IIP only supports automatic and algorithmic defined load profile which is sent to each energy storage controller – either to the battery controller or to the boiler controller. However, the systems used by Albena can provide for manual setting of the load profile to each hot water energy storage installation. These manual settings have granularity of 1 hour. The reason for this is that the Bulgarian energy market (IBEX) works with 1-hour granularity of price per volume values.

The scope of the test is as follows:

1. Randomly pick a hot water system from those which have been converted to be IIP connection ready.
2. Using the hot water system software interface define a 24-hour load profile to be performed in kWh.
3. Wait for execution of the predefined 24-hour profile.
4. After the predefined 24-hour load profile setting has elapsed, compare the resulting measured load profile from the electrical meter and ensure it matches the predefined load profile from the software interface setting.

NOTE: Before performing a test at a different hot water installation, its boiler configuration, water piping insulation and power capabilities must be analysed.

5.7.2 Baseline (quantified)

Each 1-hour slot of the 24-hour predefined load profile can always have a minimum of 0kWh energy consumption; however, the maximum can vary based on the boiler system configuration. In this case, we've picked the test to be performed at hotel Gergana. Hotel Gergana has a total of 9 boilers, which collectively have a maximum power of 86kW. The resulting consumption per each hour block should be between 0kWh and 86kWh.

5.7.3 Target value (with threshold)

Once the predefined load profile has been set (as pictured below), we expect the results to follow it. However, the marginal error is expected to be high. The reason is twofold. Firstly, hotel Gergana is an old hotel and has a fairly old water heater installation which has been retrofitted with a hot water system manager ready to be connected to the IIP. This means that the piping insulation throughout the hotel is still quite poor, and we expect energy loss due to the piping. Secondly, hotel Gergana has a constant recirculation flow of the prepared hot water, which is to ensure that hotel guests get hot water quickly as soon as they turn the tap on, regardless of which floor they are on. While this is a requirement for our hotel, it is incurring quite significant water heat losses. However, providing exceptional services to our guests is a requirement, which means that the prepared domestic hot water temperature must always be above a certain minimum, and hot water recirculation must always be employed.

Considering the requirements above, a successful test would be if the resulting consumption values are between 0 and 86kWh for each hour block, and if the values match the set predefined curve with an expected marginal error.

We've ran tests with a thermostat setting of 55 C° for the prepared domestic hot water output and without connecting the system to the IIP or using a predefined load profile. We've found that roughly 40kWh per our energy is needed constantly to satisfy the energy loss induced due to the hot water recirculation.

Figure 75: Predefined load profile for Hotel Gergana

5.7.4 Reached value

Figure 76: Predefined load profile results for Hotel Gergana

The results of the test are shown in the graph below. As can be seen from the graph, they match the high consumption of 86kWh nearly perfectly, while the low consumption of 0kWh could hardly be matched.

5.7.5 Conclusion

The test is considered a success; however, some important findings have been discovered:

- Hotel requirements of always serving a minimum temperature domestic hot water to guests currently prevent us to strictly honour the predefined load profile. We only have one mean to produce domestic hot water at this hotel (no RES or alternative sources), which is another important reason for not being able to duly comply.
- Right after 8:00 local time, the boilers have enough energy to significantly lower the generally needed consumption for recirculation of around 40kWh per each hour. However, even though the boilers should be switched off, the consumption gradually increases as is expected. This is not so notable at 19:00, which is due to both smaller time of heating boilers (3hrs vs. 5hs in the morning), and water usage by hotel guests in the afternoon.

We've also discovered areas for improvement, which however are related not to the software system itself, but to the hot water installation:

- Improve piping insulation.
- Increase boiler capacity to provide more hot water storage.

6 Spain: Pilot in EPESA

General KPIs

6.1 Test: Prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”

6.1.1 Purpose

To prove the benefits of using open standard protocols and reducing the possibilities of brand specific customizations. It's important to avoid local “tailor-made” solutions that will influence on the scalability, both in time and in re-structuring of register/database. Applies to all use-cases.

6.1.2 Abstract

Standard defined methodology used to reduce time of adaptation in scaling up the pilots. This KPI should prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”.

6.1.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

Installation ready for test and supporting the test steps.

6.1.4 Test steps

The test steps presented in Table 3 intend to quantify the effort of some of the steps of the process of implementing the InvaDE platform at a site. The intention with these tests is to measure the time and standardization of this implementation, so the scalability of the platform could be validated.

The first steps (1 - 6) were performed during the configuration of the EPESA pilot architecture in the InvaDE platform, whereas the last steps consist on theoretical scenarios, where the system performance is validated with higher volumes of users in the platform.

Table 38 - Test steps: timeframe for adapting new customers

	Description	Expected result	Result
1	Add new recipient of flexibility	Flexibility customer established within 5 minutes	Successful
2	Define contract between FO and flex recipient	Contract established within 10 minutes	Successful
3	Check communication through open standards and protocols between recipient and FO according to contract defined	Recipient is able to execute and communicate instructions according to contracts (latency < 5 seconds)	Successful
4	Add new flexibility provider	Flexibility provider established within 5 minutes	Successful
5	Define contract between FO and flex provider	Contract established within 10 minutes.	Not applied
6	Check communication based open standards and protocols between flex provider and FO according to contract defined	FO is able to execute and communicate instructions according to contract (latency < 1 seconds)	Successful
7	Repeat steps 1-3 for 5 different randomly picked recipients	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	Successful
8	Repeat steps 4-6 for 10 flexibility providers	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	Successful

Step one was performed successfully in less than 5 minutes. In the EPESA pilot there are represented two roles which make use of the flexibility, these roles were created during the platform configuration and can be seen in image below.

EPESA and MERCATOR are added as counterparties in the platform, with the roles of DSO and BRP respectively.

Name	Address	Type	Organization No	Status
EyPESA	Carrer del Rec 28 Barcelo...	Company	535	Active
FO		Company	614	Active
MERCATOR	Carrer del Rec 28 Barcelo...	Company	281	Active

Figure 77 – Recipients of flexibility - EPESA pilot (IIP screenshot)

Step two was also executed according with the expected results, where a contract was established between the FO and each one of the flexibility recipients. It is important to

note that this step can only be validated in a conceptual level. Due to the fact that the role of the FO is not yet legal in Spain, the validation of this step within the real conditions is not possible. Nevertheless, the capacity of the Invade platform to cope with this need was validated. Contracts were configured in the platform in less than 10 minutes (Figure 78). In this step it is important to note that, despite the technical viability of the platform to allow setting up these contracts, the terms in which they rule consist of a lot of different possibilities that can go from establishing fixed fees between parties, penalizations for not complying with the agreements or the formation of the prices for the flexibility traded. All these possibilities consist of a range of scenarios with interest and potential for further development.

Flex contracts									
Contract Types		Search		Delivery At Date	01.08.2019		Available At Date	01.08.2019	
Name ↑	Contract Type	Owner	Counterparty	Buy/Sell	Delivery...	Delivery...	Availabl...	Availabl...	
Contract between FO and BRP	BRPOptimization	FO	MERCATOR	Sell	31.12.2018	31.12.2020	31.12.2018	31.12.2020	
Contract between FO and DSO	DSOOptimization	FO	EyPESA	Sell	30.12.2018	30.12.2020	30.12.2018	30.12.2020	

Figure 78 – contracts established between FO and flexibility recipients (IIP screenshot)

Third step intends to verify if there is any latency within the communication between the FO and the flexibility recipients. This step could be verified once the integration of the Invade platform with EPESA's systems was completed. It was verified that all communications (bi-directional) were executed instantaneously, i.e. control signals generated by the platform were immediately received in the pilot systems, as well as the requests for flexibility generated by the two users reach the Invade platform within the same second. Figure illustrates the lack of latency within the communications of the FO and the flexibility recipients. In the picture, one can see a list with flexibility request messages being sent by the DSO to the FO, where the *Created Time* field corresponds to the time in which the message was created in EPESA and the *Message Date Time* column has the timestamp in which the message arrived to the Invade platform, being possible to verify that the communication is instantaneous.

Message Date Time	Entity Status	From Time	To Time	AssetCode	MessageSequence	ComputedMessageId	Created Time	Modified Time
2019-07-17T08:14:04Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	19.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	63698944042491916987		17.07.2019 10:14	
2019-07-17T07:13:36Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	19.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989444359469794		17.07.2019 09:13	
2019-07-17T06:15:57Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	6369894405577894963		17.07.2019 06:15	
2019-07-17T05:12:06Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	19.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	63698937126379772		17.07.2019 07:12	
2019-07-17T04:16:02Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	19.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989337638498160		17.07.2019 06:16	
2019-07-17T03:12:26Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	19.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989299474056535		17.07.2019 05:12	
2019-07-17T03:10:12Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	Flexibility Area Spain	636989298140505243		17.07.2019 05:10	
2019-07-17T02:14:04Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	19.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989254450835059		17.07.2019 04:14	
2019-07-17T01:13:26Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	19.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989228073810045		17.07.2019 03:13	
2019-07-17T00:13:32Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	19.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989192132897071		17.07.2019 02:13	
2019-07-16T23:15:16Z	Active	18.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989112174301915		17.07.2019 01:15	
2019-07-16T22:19:54Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989123951470988		17.07.2019 00:19	
2019-07-16T21:16:00Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989065671732270		16.07.2019 23:16	
2019-07-16T20:18:51Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989051328678503		16.07.2019 22:18	
2019-07-16T19:15:13Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636989013143048343		16.07.2019 21:15	
2019-07-16T18:14:31Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988976727071127		16.07.2019 20:14	
2019-07-16T17:16:03Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988941644519645		16.07.2019 19:16	
2019-07-16T16:17:41Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988936329189569		16.07.2019 18:17	
2019-07-16T16:00:20.856	Active	15.07.2019 00:00	16.07.2019 00:00	Flexibility Area Spain	63698889620559387		16.07.2019 18:00	
2019-07-16T16:00:00.456	Active	15.07.2019 00:00	16.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	63698889600459954		16.07.2019 18:00	
2019-07-16T15:22:32Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988873542085442		16.07.2019 17:22	
2019-07-16T14:17:04Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	63698883425566368		16.07.2019 16:17	
2019-07-16T13:22:07Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988801284886374		16.07.2019 15:22	
2019-07-16T12:18:32Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988763150002129		16.07.2019 14:18	
2019-07-16T11:20:40Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988728497145131		16.07.2019 13:20	
2019-07-16T10:16:11Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	63698869319402094		16.07.2019 12:16	
2019-07-16T09:18:02Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988684946012068		16.07.2019 11:18	
2019-07-16T08:15:38Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988617390047428		16.07.2019 10:15	
2019-07-16T07:17:40Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988582619348651		16.07.2019 09:17	
2019-07-16T06:15:07Z	Active	17.07.2019 00:00	18.07.2019 00:00	DSOZoneSpain	636988544432299925		16.07.2019 08:15	

Figure 79– No latency within communications between FO and flexibility recipients (IIP screenshot)

Step four, verifies the adaptability of the platform to add new flexibility providers. The flexibility provider within the EPESA pilot is the battery, and it was done during the configuration of the pilot architecture. The InvaDE platform allows to make this configuration either manually or via API. In the EPESA pilot it was done manually, and it took less than 5 minutes. When doing this configuration, all characteristics of the battery and PED which are indispensable for the battery optimization are specified, such as the battery installed capacity, battery and PED efficiency, etc. (Figure 80). Important to note that in the future scenario of increasing the number of flexibility sources, this step should be done via the automatic configuration to optimize the time.

AssetPropertyClassifica...	PropertyName	Value
Storage	Installed Max Capacity	200.45
Storage	Installed Min Capacity	100
Storage	Max Charging Power	100
Storage	Max Discharging Power	100
Storage	Min Charging Power	
Storage	Min Discharging Power	
Storage	Efficiency of Charging	0.97
Storage	Efficiency of Discharging	0.97
Storage	Threshold Charge	0.9
Storage	Threshold Discharge	0.5
Storage	Threshold Stored Energy ...	1
Storage	Cost Charging	0
Storage	Cost Discharging	0.141
Storage	Startup Time	0
Storage	Shutdown Time	0
Storage	Efficiency Of Charging Inv...	0.96
Storage	EfficiencyOfDischargingIn...	0.96

Figure 80 - configuration of flexibility source in the platform (IIP screenshot)

Step five is not applied in the EPESA pilot due to the inexistence of a battery owner role within the pilot architecture. Within the pilot, the battery is assumed to be property of the FO and therefore no contracts are established between them. Nevertheless, this is noted to be an important point to further develop, once regulations regarding FO and ownership of storage assets by DSO's have further improvements.

Step six verifies if there is any latency between the control signals sent from the FO and the real operation of the flexibility assets. This step was verified and validated during one of the integration tests executed during the pilot implementation. During this test, control signals were sent from the Invade platform to the system which manages the battery and the immediate activation of the battery was verified (see chapter 6.2.4 for test results).

Steps seven and eight were executed within a theoretical scenario, where there is one battery in each secondary substation providing flexibility to the distribution grid. This step is applied only at a platform level, meaning that the flexibility providers are added in the platform as testing assets and the verification of its stability is done.

6.1.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The implementation of the Invade platform and its scalability should be, as far as possible, an easy and standard process in order to ensure it is not a specific solution which would not adapt to a possible growing market. To measure and verify the “adaptability” of this platform to the process of including new customers, there are several aspects to take into consideration and therefore two main scenarios are considered: baseline scenario, which corresponds to the architecture implemented within the EPESA pilot, and a large-scale scenario, where the inclusion of further assets and flexibility recipients are considered. Scenario one was measured and commented in the previous section following the test steps provided in Table 3 whereas scenario two is described in section 6.1.7 and commented in section 6.1.8.

6.1.6 Baseline

The baseline scenario is considered to be the one implemented in the pilot, where there are three main roles which interchange flexibility and there is one flexibility source. The roles, as described in previous documents, are the DSO, BRP and the FO, whereas the flexibility source is the 210-kWh stationary battery installed at the secondary substation of the company's headquarters.

One can see in Figure the grid topology of the EPESA pilot. This grid consists in one primary substation and 12 secondary substations. The flexibility source of this pilot is

Figure 82 - large-scale scenario – grid topology

6.1.8 Reached value

In order to measure and comment the adaptability of the Invade platform to acquire new customers, one should have in mind what is the hierarchical distribution of the assets within the platform. Figure 83 represents this hierarchy and highlights the assets which were configured in the EPESA pilot, this represents the baseline scenario.

Figure 83 - hierarchy of assets within the Invade platform

Once this structure is implemented at a site, in case of scaling up with more resources or flexibility recipients, the only necessary thing to add is the new resource/user (as long as it is within the same site). The rest of the platform configuration doesn't need to change. For example, in the case of the EPESA pilot, if we want to add one solar PV to the system, we first need to configure the weather area and it needs to be integrated with the weather data; at the same time the resource *Generation* can be added and integrated. In the future, any other PV to be added to the system doesn't require more than adding and integrating the resource in the platform, because the weather area and data are the same.

If one compares it with the large-scale scenario, in terms of platform configuration, adding new flexibility providers (11 more batteries) would not require more than configuring 11 more assets type *Resource – Storage*. This would require knowing the characteristics of all batteries and introducing them in the platform (either manually or via the API). In terms of integration, in this scenario, the batteries would be controlled through the same SCADA system of the DSO that controls the battery of the baseline scenario. Therefore, the communication channels with the Invade platform would remain the same, while the differentiation to which resource send the control signals would be done within the user's system.

Figure represents, in a visual format, the control management of the battery in the baseline scenario. Control signals are sent from the Invade platform to the flexibility management system (FMS) through HTTPS, which then redirects them to the SCADA system via WSDL. From the SCADA the signals are sent to the power electronics device (PED) via MODBUS TCP IP and then to the battery via CAN bus.

Figure 84- baseline scenario – battery control

Figure 85 represents the same visual scheme in the large-scale scenario, where it is possible to have the idea that in terms of effort in integrating with the Invade platform this is minimum; while the differentiation of the control signals of the batteries would be done either at FMS or SCADA level.

Figure 85 - Large-scale scenario – batteries control

6.1.9 Conclusion

The main conclusion of this test is that the Invade platform is a product easily adapted to different architecture setups. In the EPESA pilot, the IIP was configured to the roles and assets tested within the pilot use case, whereas it was also seen that the same platform can be configured in a different setup such as the ones implemented in the different pilots. It was seen that the process of setting up new clients inside the IIP is straight forward, as well as setting up the contracts within the platform.

Although it is validated that the step of configuring the real setup within the IIP is not time consuming and can be easily scaled up, one should not depreciate the time needed for the integration of the users' systems with the platform. Which, depending on the user, can be more or less time consuming.

6.2 Test: demonstrate the improvements of using batteries

6.2.1 Purpose

This is a comparative test. To demonstrate the improvement of using batteries due to better % usage, and at the same time reduce the probability of black outs. Lower safety margin and maximum utilization in the installation to reduce power-peaks.

6.2.2 Abstract

KPIs proving the reduction of the vulnerability in latency by using batteries in households.

KPI= actual response / theoretical response with no latency

This implies that the response time for compensation of loss of power is measured and compared to a pilot requirement or theoretical standard.

6.2.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

“Theoretical response” has been defined.

Amp meter connected to the battery.

6.2.4 Test steps

Table 39 - Test steps – improvements of using batteries

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Send activation signal from FO. Start clock at point of activation.	Activation executed. Clock started.	Successful
2.	Monitor the amp meter connected to the battery. Record time to amp meter change- Record the response time and meter reading at activation.	Response time reading Amp meter reading	Successful – instantaneous activation
3.	Rerun test in the following manner: Simulating a black out.		Successful
4.	Disconnect power. Simulate black out		-
5.	Repeat steps 1-3		-

6.2.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The measurement procedure to evaluate the benefits of using batteries in the distribution grid is defined in the previous table. These tests intend to verify the possibility of real-time remote control of the batteries and therefore improvements for the distribution grid through different scenarios in which they can be applied. The first test applied in this case intends to verify the immediateness of the battery remote control, while the second test intends to verify the technical possibility of the battery to supply a load in island mode for a certain period.

6.2.6 Baseline (quantified)

This scenario does not have a quantifiable baseline.

6.2.7 Target value (with threshold)

The targets in this indicator are not quantifiable in quantitative terms, nevertheless there are two clear objectives for each one of the tests:

- Test 1 (activation signal from FO): the objective is to verify that there exists no latency between the control signal sent from the FO and the battery activation.
- Test 2 (simulate black out): the objective is to verify the usage of the battery as back up support in case of an electrical failure.

6.2.8 Reached value

Step one and two were successfully executed, and the target was validated. The remote control of the battery through the Invade platform is done with no latency.

Figure illustrates the evolution of the SOC of the battery during the test registered in the battery management system. It is possible to observe a first decrease and increase of the SOC at the beginning of the test, which represents the first test of remote control for discharging and charging. The last sudden decrease/increase of the SOC corresponds to a second validation test of the latency in execution.

Figure 86- battery SOC evolution during integration test

Figure 87 illustrates the SOC of the battery (in kWh) represented in the Invade platform during the day of the integration test. This SOC evolution does not account with the sudden variations of the SOC provoked by the previous test because they were executed in less than 15 minutes, and the SOC timeseries are updated from the battery to the Invade platform with a 15 minutes frequency. Nevertheless, it is possible to see the evolution of the energy levels of the battery during the test.

Figure 87 - battery time series in the Invade platform, during integration test (IIP screenshot)

The second test was validated through continuous discharge of the battery and consequent validation of the compliance of all safety parameters of its operation, such as the maintenance of the battery’s average cell temperatures within the optimum range. A validation of the reverse cycle was also performed, through a continuous charge of the battery inside its limits of DoD

Figure 88 - SOC evolution of battery charging for half cycle

Figure 89 - Output power variation during test

Figure 90 - evolution of cell temperatures (average)

6.2.9 Conclusion

The current test validates the fact that the battery can be remotely controlled by the Invade platform keeping all operation standards within the optimal limits. This test is valuable especially in the DSO scenario, because for the DSO it is very important to have full control over the flexibility assets, meaning that there should be no delay between the flexibility requested by the DSO and the time in which the flexibility is actually delivered/consumed to/from the grid. In the current scenario, the DSO flexibility requests intend to alleviate the DSO’s grid of any predicted congestions, i.e. ensuring the voltage

and power are always within the optimal limits. The FO ensures to provide an optimal service when making sure to have a complete control over its flexibility assets.

It also validates the fact that it is possible to use a stationary battery to provide backup services to a critical building, by continuously discharging electricity to the grid maintaining all security parameters controlled, over a large period.

6.3 Test: measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling by including a battery

6.3.1 Purpose

This test will measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling of including the whole systems PED + battery as part of an installation. This should be done at secondary substation level.

Special focus is put on voltage quality in connection with storage system with particular interest in voltage level, flicker, unbalance and harmonics.

The noise affectation at PLC level of the EMF could affect at the DCU and smart meters technologies install in the DSO network. Based on measurements in representative positions in the secondary substation, it can be concluded that the electric and magnetic fields caused by PED is not affecting at PLC telecommunications level.

6.3.2 Abstract

KPI will prove the quality-improvement of including the whole system, PED + battery in the installation. Reflecting the standards of quality measuring like:

Limiting max. voltage level on grid connection point to a given level given by law or standard.

6.3.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

In many countries maximum and minimum voltage levels are given by law or standard. In Spain the appliances in household and industrial consumers must operate within a voltage range of 230V+/- 7%.

In addition, according with the Spanish law, the voltage increments caused by decentralized generation installed in the medium or low voltage grid should not be higher than 2.5% of the nominal voltage of the correspondent connection point.

6.3.4 Test steps

One of the objectives of this test was to perform a field test in order to verify the ability of the PED to regulate the active and reactive power in order to have an influence over the voltage levels. During this test 21 different combinations of injecting/consuming active/reactive power were tested, and the voltage measured in each one of them. The result values are expressed in Table 40 below.

Table 40 – Test steps – voltage control

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	PED stop	DCU collecting data Measure the PRIME frequency spectrum	Link status
2.	PED working 25%	DCU collecting data Measure the PRIME frequency spectrum	Link status
3.	PED working 50%	DCU collecting data Measure the PRIME frequency spectrum	Link status
4.	PED working 75%	Voltage decreases or increases and reach target value	Link status

6.3.5 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The measurement procedure follows the steps indicated in the table of the previous sub-chapter. The measurement period of the sample presented in table 4 is less than 3 minutes for each control signal/measurement.

For the current test, the following equipment was used:

- CVM LV Bus bar
- Additional analysed
- MV transformer
- Oscilloscope

By law, in Spain, the voltage levels should not be outside a range of +/-7% respect to the nominal values. This implies that the voltage should not be higher than 246,1 Vca nor lower than 213,4 Vca.

6.3.6 Baseline (quantified)

Assigned or nominal value.

6.3.7 Target value (with threshold)

This test does not have a quantifiable target value because it is a field test and not an indicator calculated based on experimental measurements. It has a well-defined objective instead, which is described in the abstract of the current chapter.

The objective of the current test is to validate the ability of the technology to modify the voltage among established limits.

In terms of Noise, that DCU still working and collecting data from SM.

6.3.8 Reached value

Table 41 -test data

P [kW]	Q [kVAr]	Rms (C1) [V]	Rms (C2) [V]	Rms (C3) [V]
0	0	234,42	232,037	228,814
25	0	235,436	232,748	229,488
25	50	239,752	237,213	234,697
25	-50	234,049	231,606	229,046
50	0	237,665	235,34	232,284
50	50	240,064	237,64	234,697
50	-50	235,284	232,717	230,142
75	0	238,508	235,982	233,289
75	25	239,19	236,454	233,732
75	-25	236,771	234,25	231,264
-75	0	234,871	232,046	229,776
-75	25	236,723	233,931	230,941
-75	-25	233,455	231,109	228,115
-50	0	235,207	232,744	230,125
-50	50	238,614	235,999	232,779
-50	-50	233,085	230,289	227,44
-25	0	236,326	233,836	230,645
-25	50	239,185	236,999	233,51
-25	-50	233,341	230,783	227,576
0	75	240,283	237,909	234,992
0	-75	232,468	230,021	227,302

Figure 91 - Voltage control (variation of Q at P constant)

Figure 92 - Voltage control (variation of P at constant Q)

Figure 93 – voltage variations during tests at pilot site

Figure 94- all PED functionalities disabled (oscilloscope screenshot – taken during tests)

Figure 95 - harmonics compensation enabled (oscilloscope screenshot – taken during tests)

Figure 96 - all PED functionalities enabled (oscilloscope screenshot – taken during tests)

6.3.9 Conclusion

A whole PED device installed to address harmonic current and reactive power problem in power systems, it can compensate both harmonic current and reactive power in the system, which greatly improves the power quality at the SS.

Compared with conventional control schemes, the INVADE EPESA pilot scheme has the advantages of being straight forward to understand and simple to implement.

The real measurements and results show the proposed control scheme has good steady state and dynamical performance. In the future, it will be investigated how to find optimal control schemes for the cases where harmonic and reactive power compensation requirements exceed the rating of active filter.

Given the future trends of the electric sector, in which decentralized generation by PV panels will have a significant increase in respect to current values, the ability of DSOs to control the voltage levels with relative flexibility is an important factor in respect to the effective management of the grids. This test proves that the ability to control assets such as batteries and PEDs with these functionalities are a valuable tool for DSOs in what concerns facing the future scenarios of the distribution grids.

Specific KPIs

6.4 Test: Congestion reduction issues

The purpose of this scenario is to evaluate the amount of congestions avoided in the pilot location over a certain period by means of activating flexibility through the flexibility operator.

6.4.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

Congestion management is a service provided by the FO to be used by the DSO with the intent of avoiding grid congestions in the MV network.

In the EPESA pilot, grid congestions are defined as events where the measured current passing in the cables is above its maximum operational limit allowed and/or the measured voltage is outside the grid operational limits (230V +/7%). It is also considered a congestion an event where it is verified an overload on the HV/MV transformer of the primary substation or in the MV/MV transformers of all other 12 secondary substations.

Within the grid topology of the EPESA pilot, and the existing loads and inexistent decentralized generation, we're under a scenario where currently there are no grid congestions observed. For testing purposes, the grid operational limits are lowered so congestions are observed under a test environment and the execution of grid congestion management services can be tested without dealing with real grid congestions. This setup allows DSOs preparing for a future scenario in which due to the trends in the electric system (increasing the share of decentralized generation, EV's, etc.), grid congestions are a much more frequent incident.

Figure 93 represents part of the DSO's SCADA system, with the representation of the primary substation E.R.REC and its connection to the secondary substation E.T.Node. The battery and PED installations are represented by the yellow rectangles, connected at the transformer of 400V. Given the current scenario, congestions in the grid can be observed in the points indicated with the white circles, such as the MV cables which connect the primary substation to the E.T.Node and the MV/LV transformer installed at the substation.

Figure 97 – topology of C.T.Node

In the EPESA pilot, to test the congestion management services, the DSO makes its own internal analysis of the current and future status of the grid in order to understand if there is any need for flexibility in order to avoid a congestion that is likely to happen in the future over the operations area.

The DSO has a data concentrator unit in each secondary substation, and a device installed in parallel which aggregates all data from the smart meters and measures (at substation level) data of active and reactive power with a frequency of 15 minutes. With this data, the DSO makes forecasts for the next 48 hours after the execution period which allows knowing in advance what will be the load at each substation.

Figure 94 is a visualization of the SCADA system, with all substations participating in the pilot which are collecting data.

Figure 99 – DSO process timeline

Figure 96 illustrates the format of a flexibility request sent by the DSO, in this case requesting only for down regulation.

The convention used in the EPESA pilot is that positive values represent flexibility requests with up regulation (charging the battery) while negative values represent requests for down regulation (battery discharge).

Figure 100 – flexibility request message of the DSO (IIP screenshot)

6.4.2 Baseline (quantified)

As mentioned previously, this is a scenario in which currently the DSO does not observe this type of problems at this particular part of the grid. Therefore, the baseline scenario cannot be quantified representing the current situation.

However, with all observed trends regarding the electricity sector, in which there is an increase in the share of decentralized generation (through small scale PV at residential level, EV's with V2G technologies, etc.) and an increasingly share of flexible loads at residential level (such as water boilers, space heaters, etc.) it is imperative to make the exercise of modelling what the future scenarios of distribution grids will be in the future, in order to propose solutions which make use of flexibility for operating the grid and eliminate the need of investing in new infrastructure.

6.4.3 Reached value

The main objective of this indicator is to assess the effectiveness of providing services of grid congestion management to the DSO under the current setup. The methodology, drafted in D10.5, intended to make a results' comparison between the congestions predicted by the DSO and the performance of the FO in solving them.

At the current phase of the project, the results don't have enough volume to draft conclusions regarding the effectiveness of such processes. However, as volume of results increase, deeper conclusions can be outlined.

Preliminary results are represented in figures below. In figure 97 both a flexibility request by the DSO and a flexibility offer by the FO are drawn in the same graph, allowing to observe that the FO has offered nearly all flexibility requested by the DSO, meaning that in this case there was nearly enough flexibility to solve the current congestion. Figure 26 illustrates a case in which most of the flexibility request was not met by the flexibility offered by the FO. Further cases should be observed to allow verification of trends and quantifying a value for the effectiveness of such implementation.

Figure 101– overlapping of flexibility requested by the DSO and flexibility offered by the FO for one day (IIP screenshot)

Figure 102 – DSO flexibility request vs flexibility offered by the FO (IIP screenshot)

Although with a low volume of results observed, so far it is seen that the DSO requests generally for down regulations, meaning that it is of its interest to discharge the battery in most of the cases. Figure 99 shows some examples of requests for flexibility from the DSO for one day. It is observed that even though the DSO makes continuous forecasts and power flow simulations, the variations of the flexibility requested are very low. All the requests for a particular day are concentrated in the last hours of the day and its magnitude does not have a big variation. It is therefore a result which indicates that increasing the forecasts' frequency does not imply on a greater precision when identifying grid congestions.

Figure 103– set of DSO flexibility requests for a period of one day - 01.10.2019 (IIP screenshot)

Figure 100 represents a sequence of six flexibility requests sent by the DSO in six consequent days.

Figure 104 – DSO flexibility requests from 28-09-2019 until 03-10-2019 (IIP screenshot)

6.4.4 Conclusion

This exercise allows to draft some conclusions relative to the methods with which DSOs can interact with external parties (such as FOs) with the objective of having an external source helping with grid management tasks.

With this scenario, the communication method between DSO and FO was implemented and tested, and the exercise of identifying which data is valuable for each party was done. A scenario was tested in which it is imperative that a DSO verifies the following criteria:

1. Has knowledge over its grid parameters and is capable of making predictions to identify the timeframes in which the grid is expected to be congested;
2. Knows the characteristics of the flexibility assets (battery+PED for the current case) which are available for providing the flexibility in the respective area of the grid. Allowing the DSO to make the previous analysis of identifying the exact amount of flexibility needed to solve the congestion.

In a larger scenario, where DSOs would identify grid congestions in more disperse areas of the grid and FOs would manage and control a wider variety of flexibility assets, it is important that the DSO can have access to the characteristics of these flexibility assets, so it can identify the ones with technical capabilities of addressing the grid congestion.

The timeframes of interaction between DSO-FO in the pilot implementation are day-ahead messages, which means that congestion management is being done always for the next day. There might be operational advantages for both parties with this scenario as both the DSO and the FO have more time to observe, correct and optimize both the grid and the flexibility assets. However, the functionalities of the Invade platform allow timeframes to be shortened and requests to be done within the current day. These scenarios are also interesting to be analysed as there might be more accuracy of the DSO forecasts and therefore more reliability on the grid congestion management. Shorter timeframes for flexibility control might be advantageous for the DSO itself as it reduces the time delay for operating the grid in case of technical problems.

Although in the EPESA pilot, the chosen area for the Invade implementation is the MV grid (which is represented in Figure 98), in future tests it would be interesting to extend it to the LV grid and assess the management of flexibility in the operation of this area of the network. In these future scenarios, the Invade platform could be used to manage and control distributed storage in the LV grid (such as distributed batteries, EV's or residential loads) which would provide the DSO the possibility to manage grid congestions and power quality over this area.

6.5 Test: Energy and power reduction

Power losses are an inherent part of electrical grids. They are a consequence of transmission and distribution of electrical energy and will always be part of any traditional electrical system. Losses do constitute an important amount of energy flows in transmission and distribution networks. With energy efficiency concerns, reduction of losses takes an increasingly important role, both for reasons of financial sustainability and for improving system quality and reliability. There is a major environmental benefit in reducing power losses. There can also be a significant economic benefit if power losses are reduced cost effectively.

In general, the understanding of losses – regardless of their origin – is that they are a representation of the difference between all the energy that is injected into a system (which includes not only generation but, in some cases, also imported energy) and the billed energy consumed (energy going out of a system would also include exports in some cases).

Energy and power reduction in electricity grids can result from various mechanisms which affect the different network components. The most common way refers to energy converted to heat in power lines and transformers, resulting from the laws of physics. Since technical losses are an outcome of technical features, they can be estimated quite accurately and are in some ways determined by the properties of the grid and its components.

The electrical distribution losses accounts for most of the power losses in the entire system. For that technical losses occur when the energy is dissipated by the equipment and conductors in the distribution lines.

Power losses can be determined in different ways: either by direct metering of the injected and withdrawn energy or by estimating the losses by calculation. If losses are determined by calculation that accomplish this by subtracting electricity withdrawals (electricity going out of the grid such as electricity for the battery connected in SS Node).

The energy losses improvement evaluates the reduction of energy technical losses in the whole chain in the distribution grid, from TSO primary substation to LV bus in secondary substation NODE. The EPESA pilot has implemented a technology which will impact positively in the reduction of energy losses. This KPI should be calculated for INVADE EPESA pilot addressing sub-functionalities focused on reducing energy losses. The reduction in energy losses will be calculated using the following formula:

$$\Delta E(\%) = \frac{E_{DIS} - E_{BAT}}{E_{DIS}}(1)$$

Where:

E_{DIS} → Energy from primary substation to SS Node

E_{BAT} → Energy provided by the battery

6.5.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The strategy for the charging and discharging should consider the excessive charging or discharging and power compensation failures, even if their energy capacities are unlimited. Control of the SoC in distribution network applications is essential. For this test a SoC control strategy is proposed in to facilitate localized control, regulate the SoC of each ESS, exploit available capacities effectively and ensure voltage regulation while avoiding saturation or stress for various operational conditions. For this test, will have appropriate charging and discharging strategies, and adherence to manufacturers' recommendations must be maintained to address the major challenges of reductions of the energy and power in all chain of the pilot, achieving maximum output, optimal efficiency, and a long lifetime.

The methodology for this test assumes the battery has an optimal charging and discharging schedule to facilitate peak load shaving in a grid system. For the proposed test model in Figure 105, the charging and discharging rules are expressed in Eq. (2), (3). This model and charging and discharging strategies are useful for integrating RES into the grid and mitigating the intermittency of renewable sources and line congestion.

Figure 105 – charging and discharging rules

F_n^L = Line power flow in step n (kW)

C_{RL} = Rated power capacity of the line (kW)

P_n^{IN} = Charge power input in step n (kW)

P_{CB}^{IN} = Rated charge capacity (kW)

P_n^{OUT} = Discharge power input in step n (kW)

P_{CB}^{OUT} = Rated discharge capacity (kW)

E_{max} = Maximum energy stored (kWh)

E_{min} = Minimum energy stored (kWh)

E_n = Energy stored in S.S.

The charging test strategy will be:

$$P_n^{IN} = \min\{(F_n^L - C_{RL}), P_{CB}^{IN}, (E_{max} - E_n)\} \quad (2)$$

When line congestion or reduction of consumption from feeder appears with the charge rate restricted by the PESSIN as well as by the ESS availability, only the ESS will be charged.

Discharging strategy:

When line congestion appears ($F_n^L - C_{RL} > 0$) with the charge rate restricted as the battery capacity availability, only the battery capacity will be charged.

Discharging strategy:

$$P_n^{OUT} = \min\{(C_{RL} - F_n^L), P_{CB}^{OUT}, (E_n - E_{min})\} \quad (3)$$

When there is no congestion or need to reduce energy and power from feeders and the discharge rate is restricted by the maximum power from PED as well as by the available line capacity, to avoid new congestion because of discharged power, then only discharging of battery capacity will occur. The discharging of ESSs continues on the condition that stored energy is available.

Importantly, a charging-discharging strategy for low-voltage distribution networks is proposed to test the energy and power reduction to provide support peak loads and valley moments in the evening.

Table 42 -test steps – energy and power reduction

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Check SoC battery	80%	77 %
2.	Generate a signal to charge the battery	Increase up to 90%	Command charge battery -60 kW (after 15 minutes checked SoC 91 %)
3.	Generate a signal to discharge the battery	Decrease up to 70%	Command discharge battery + 20 kW (after 60 minutes checked SoC 71 %)
4.	Obtain the module value and signal of the current	+/- A	Step-2 +30 A Step-3
5.	Check the contribution in LV bus bar in SS.	A, V	Before step 2 & 3: V Bus= 403 V A Bus= -216 A Step-2: V Bus= 400 V A Bus= -302 A Step-3: V Bus= 405 V A Bus= -187 A
6.	Check the contribution in MV feeder in PS	A, V	Before step 2 & 3: V Feeder= 20,5 kV A Feeder= + 47 A Step-2: V Feeder= 20,5 V A Feeder= + 48 A Step-3: V Feeder= 20,5 V A Feeder= + 46 A
7.	Model and simulate for the other 10 SS.	-	Before step 2 & 3: V Feeder= 20,5 kV A Feeder= + 48 A Step-2: V Feeder= 20,1 V A Feeder= + 63 A Step-3: V Feeder= 20,6 V A Feeder= + 41 A

6.5.2 Baseline (quantified)

According the maximum capacity of the network losses defined by the equation (4),

$$E_{p_i} = [3 \cdot r_{1Si} \cdot L_{1Si} \cdot I_{feeder}^2] \cdot T_{eq} \quad (4)$$

E_{p_i} = Losses energy

r_{1Si} = Average resistance cable first step or segment

L_{1Si} = Long cable first step or segment

I_{feeder} = Feeder current

T_{eq} = Equivalent time of losses

6.5.3 Reached value

For 30 A in the feeder, the losses of the first stem are 243Wh

For 2.7 A provided from battery the contribution of reduction of the losses are 7.87Wh

The baseline from first step will be:

$$\Delta E(\%) = 1 - \left(\frac{E_{DIS} - E_{BAT}}{E_{DIS}} \right) = 1 - \left(\frac{243 \text{ Wh} - 7,87 \text{ Wh}}{243 \text{ Wh}} \right) = 4\% \quad (5)$$

6.5.4 Conclusion

The main conclusion of this indicator is the validation of the advantages of shortening the distance between electricity generation and consumption. As described above, associated with the energy transport and distribution there are thermal losses, which increase linearly with the distance travelled. The other factor which contributes greatly to the energy losses is the current. As seen in eq. 4 the energy losses increase with the square of the current. With this test, it is proven that having the type of setups as the one represented in the EPESA pilot can bring benefits to the DSO in terms of reducing the energy losses of its distribution system.

6.6 Islanding Time

In the EPESA pilot this scenario is tested. The control centre room of the DSO is considered a critical building, since, from here, the distribution grid of EPESA is monitored and controlled 24/7. At present, this room is backed up by a diesel generator, which ensures the power supply in case of an eventual electric failure.

In this scenario, the use of the energy from the battery is tested as a backup electricity source of the control centre room, avoiding thus the usage of the diesel generator and the consequent CO₂ emissions.

6.6.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

During the pilot tests, 50% of the battery capacity (about 100 kWh) is reserved to give back-up service to the critical building, whereas the other 50% is used by the FO to provide flexibility services to the DSO and the BRP.

The test of controlled islanding will be done in a real environment, following the test steps described.

Table 43 -test steps - controlled islanding test

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Check available capacity battery	100kWh are reserved and available for this test	101 kWh
2.	Check consumption critical building doesn't exceed the maximum PED power (100 kW)	- Consumptions 47 kVA - Current= 69 A - Voltage F ₁ -F ₂ = 406 V F ₂ -F ₃ = 402 V F ₃ -F ₁ = 403 V F ₁ -N= 234 V F ₂ -N= 232 V F ₃ -N= 233 V	Consumptions 31 kVA - Current= 45 A - Voltage F ₁ -F ₂ = 406 V F ₂ -F ₃ = 402 V F ₃ -F ₁ = 403 V F ₁ -N= 234 V F ₂ -N= 232 V F ₃ -N= 233 V
3.	Ensure that critical loads are connected under UPS systems	Control Centre Room servers 5 kVA Control Centre Videowall 2 kVA Control Centre Telecommunications equipment 2 kVA Control Centre lighting 3 kVA Climatic Server Room 35 kVA	Control Centre Room servers 3 kVA Control Centre Videowall 2 kVA Control Centre Telecommunications equipment 2 kVA Control Centre lighting 2 kVA Climatic Server Room 22 kVA
4.	Check the PED is synchronized to loads	SLAVE mode	SLAVE mode
5.	Send command to open LV SW gear to grid. Switch to mode island PED and	LV switch gear open three phases. Switch PED MASTER mode	Switch gear opened three phases. PED in MASTER Mode
6.	Monitoring parameters among expected values according: U, P, Q, Hz	Consumptions 31 kVA P= 29,94 kW Q= 8,23 kVAR - Current= 45 A - Voltage	Consumptions 29 kVA P= 28,7 kW Q= 3,53 kVAR - Current= 42 A - Voltage

		F ₁ -F ₂ = 401 V F ₂ -F ₃ = 401 V F ₃ -F ₁ = 401 V F ₁ -N= 231 V F ₂ -N= 231 V F ₃ -N= 231 V	F ₁ -F ₂ = 401 V F ₂ -F ₃ = 401 V F ₃ -F ₁ = 401 V F ₁ -N= 231 V F ₂ -N= 231 V F ₃ -N= 231 V
7.	Monitoring SoC Battery	SoC 47%	SoC 47%
8.	Monitoring SoC Battery (60 min)	SoC 33%	SoC 36%
9.	After 75 minutes, synchronize PED to Grid	Check: V-V'= 0 V φ=0° Hz=0 mHz	Check: V-V'= 405-400= 5 V φ=0,23° Hz=0,01 mHz
10.	Switch in mode slave PED	LV switch gear close three phases. Switch PED SLAVE mode	Switch gear closed three phases. PED in SLAVE Mode
11.	Monitoring suitable functionalities	Consumptions 31 kVA P= 29,94 kW Q= 8,23 kVAR - Current= 45 A - Voltage F ₁ -F ₂ = 401 V F ₂ -F ₃ = 401 V F ₃ -F ₁ = 401 V F ₁ -N= 231 V F ₂ -N= 231 V F ₃ -N= 231 V SoC= 33%	Consumptions 28 kVA P= 28,4 kW Q= 7,86 kVAR - Current= 41 A - Voltage F ₁ -F ₂ = 407 V F ₂ -F ₃ = 403 V F ₃ -F ₁ = 404 V F ₁ -N= 235 V F ₂ -N= 233 V F ₃ -N= 233 V SoC= 32%

6.6.2 Baseline (quantified)

This test does not have a baseline scenario. The objective of the current test is to validate the technical possibilities of operating the critical building in island mode, with support from the Invade battery instead of the diesel generator.

6.6.3 Target value (with threshold)

The whole system will be able to provide electricity for 60 minutes with a power of 100 kW. The test switches up to 50 % of the critical building consumption, that means for a power of 50 kW with a SoC of 100%, the battery provides electricity for two hours maintaining the voltage among 400 V.

With a consumption of 50 kW, after 2 hours, the SoC will never reach a value which is less than 50% of the total capacity of the battery. The Voltage must be kept among 400 V +/- 7%.

6.6.4 Reached value

The system has demonstrated the capacity to operate in island mode and guarantee up to two hours of electricity in the main head quarter building, providing up to 50 kW for two hours.

The whole equipment with the intelligent system is able to select the network that keeps operated from the battery, taking into account the signals provided from Invade platform.

The outcomes in the project has shown that batteries can improve supply continuity in contingences or planned works. The batteries are, in short, complementary to conventional local operation.

According the reached values, the whole system has been able to provide 30 kW to 50 kW for one hour, keeping the quality of service among legal limits and reacting successfully with the internal consumption.

The control centre room maximum loads involved in the test has been the followings:

- Servers: 5 kVA.
- Control Centre Videowall: 2 kVA
- Control Centre Telecommunications equipment: 2 kVA
- Control Centre lighting: 3 kVA
- Climatic Server Room 35: kVA

The reaction of the system for 60 minutes according the consumption of the critical building in island mode providing electricity from battery is shown in the following figure:

Figure 106

The State of Charge departing from 50 % of the system for 60 minutes according the consumption of the critical building in island mode providing electricity from battery is shown in the following figure:

Figure 107

The voltage behaviour coming from 50 % of SoC with the variability of the loads of the critical building 60 minutes in island mode providing electricity from battery is shown in the following figure:

Figure 108

6.6.5 Conclusion

The fundamental conclusion we can get from this test is that the facilities isolated from network to provide critical building supply mixed for another proposal such as provide BRP and DSO flexibility service are technologically as economically feasible alternative to fixed gen-set system.

The achievement of the project set allows the procedure to move from grid-connect to island mode and coming to grid-connected mode providing safely to critical building loads. We have identified data that are necessary to define de minimum size of storage to improve the investment level for this proposal, therefore the procedures have been applied to real case. Also, different successive simulations of the installation have been carried out so that has been able to study the influence of different parameters on the installation cost.

6.7 Test 4: BRP cost savings

Self-balancing portfolio optimization is a scenario with the aim of lowering the imbalance costs of the BRP, by activating flexibility. Within the EPESA pilot, as described with more detail in D10.5, the BRP makes its internal forecasts to identify the quantity of flexibility needed and interacts daily with the Invade platform to request for the respective flexibility. This interaction takes the form of a flexibility request. The main goal of the BRP with the Invade platform is to lower its imbalance costs.

In order to improve the quantification of the flexibility requests of the BRP, a model for forecasting the direction of the electric system deviation was developed with the intention of being used by the BRP as a decision tool for when to activate flexibility or not. This model was then integrated with the BRP's forecasting model and, by providing anticipated knowledge in respect to the direction of the deviation of the electric system, allows the BRP to request for flexibility if its portfolio deviation is against the system. Figure below represents in a conceptual level the interaction of the BRP with the Invade platform.

Figure 109 – conceptual scheme of the BRP scenario in the EPESA pilot

6.7.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

To evaluate the impact of the Invade platform in the BRP's imbalance costs, an economic study was conducted. In this study it is assumed that the BRP has the model for predicting the direction of the deviations of the electric system and can interact with the Invade platform to request for flexibility.

In this study, the annual total cost to be paid by predicting incorrectly the system's deviation should be inferior than the total real cost for deviations. This study was carried out with data from 2017 and follows the reasoning presented in figure below.

Figure 110 – Flow diagram of the economic study of the predictive model

This study was carried out taking into consideration the best possible scenario, where the BRP’s flexibility requests are always accepted by the FO and there are no costs associated with using the flexibility.

6.7.2 Baseline

The baseline scenario is a scenario representing the real situation of the BRP, where the energy for its clients is bought in the day-ahead market based on internal forecasts, and there are penalizations due to imbalances assumed by the BRP.

6.7.3 Reached value

The study was applied using MERCATOR’s data relative to the year 2017. The real total costs with penalizations due to imbalances were compared with the costs which MERCATOR would have had if it had applied this model.

By applying the current study, it is concluded that the predictions model implies on a cost reduction in imbalances for the BRP, where in the best possible scenario the BRP could save up until 30.57% comparing with the baseline scenario.

6.7.4 Conclusion

With this indicator it can be concluded that there is a potential for this type of solutions for BRP's. In the current electricity market situation, where BRPs are responsible for the imbalances through financial penalizations, all mechanisms which allow the BRPs to have more predictability over the imbalances and mechanisms that make possible to act and correct them with almost real time are much valuable. We're witnessing a scenario where the evolution in information technologies associated with improvements in energy storage systems seem to provide benefits for the electric system.

It is worth noticing that, as mentioned above, this study considers the best possible scenario, where there are no costs associated with using the flexibility from the Invade battery and all requests are satisfied over the testing period. In a more realistic situation there might be the case where the BRPs' flexibility requests are not all met (being because the FO needs to satisfy requests in different directions from other market participants who have priority, because there is no energy available at the time requested or due to other reasons). In these situations, even though the BRP has the capacity to identify its flexibility needs, the system might not be able to have them available and therefore the imbalance penalizations are not avoided. The other assumption considered, regarding the price to be paid by each flexibility request, is an important point to note when modelling a scenario like this. This point depends heavily on the business model adopted and different scenarios can be defined where different market entities have different responsibilities when it comes to pricing the flexibility. For example, the FO might find profitable in its business model to offer all flexibility to its customers and charge instead for a fixed monthly fee to cover the expenses; or it could find a model where there is profitability in pricing flexibility individually but adding contract costs to establish fixed fees that cover unexpected events. The definition of the terms in which this model occurs are important to define the costs of the flexibility and therefore make more realistic approaches when it comes to quantifying cost savings for BRPs.

It is also concluded from this study that still some maturation is needed in market mechanisms to allow this type of solutions to be possible. In the EPESA case, as previously mentioned, it is not yet possible for an entity such as the FO to make flexibility assets available for any market participant and therefore, for this type of solution to be applied, evaluations in this line would need to occur as well.

6.8 Test 5: Capacity of the Grid

The objective of this indicator is to evaluate and quantify the % of increase in hosting capacity of the InvaDE solution in comparison with the baseline.

6.8.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

This analysis, hosting capacity is considered as the amount of generation (kW) that can be added to the system without violating the grid operational limit and without having to undertake any grid expansion.

This indicator is simulated with the software Power Factory in which the Catalan pilot grid is drawn and the implications of different penetrations of PV are assessed.

Several power Flow simulations are done with increasing levels of distributed generation penetration and it is identified that the highest levels of stress in the pilot grid occur during 15:00h and 16:00h in the line 2021 which is the line which connects the primary substation to the secondary substation Node.

2	2.2162468	4.5445411	6.5341019	6.7513571	6.7598853	6.4902247	4.6221778	2.2305103	0.5472924	0.4125314	1.1
6	2.8332193	5.956529	8.5273312	8.8273564	8.818614	8.4746004	5.9730952	2.855566	0.6480378	0.5749762	1.5
2	3.9958982	8.4275378	11.957372	12.425058	12.382292	11.879462	8.2463551	3.8556656	0.7680685	0.7990856	1.9
9	13.660999	29.012624	41.299914	43.878497	44.055626	41.563447	28.668825	12.965611	2.2514209	3.5054542	5.9
1	2.8332194	5.9565291	8.5273313	8.8273565	8.8186141	8.4746005	5.9730953	2.8555661	0.6480379	0.5749761	1.5
2	1.6972647	3.485736	4.9506457	5.1365611	5.14555	4.9674076	3.5289213	1.7553367	0.4013692	0.2965222	0.8
4	13.848203	29.409879	41.868658	44.47676	44.671088	42.175655	29.118438	13.213035	2.3286781	3.4860198	5.9
9	15.798722	33.561672	47.820104	49.924697	50.154306	48.171331	33.296992	15.237893	2.7934789	3.7193494	6.5
7	13.660998	29.012624	41.299914	43.878497	44.055626	41.563447	28.668825	12.965611	2.2514207	3.5054543	5.9
5	10.710919	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365457	32.520271	22.442785	10.348904	1.994339	2.419345	4.5
1	10.71092	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365458	32.520271	22.442786	10.348904	1.9943395	2.4193445	4.5
2	10.71092	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365458	32.520271	22.442786	10.348904	1.9943396	2.4193444	4.5
8	3.9958977	8.4275373	11.957372	12.425057	12.382291	11.879461	8.2463546	3.8556651	0.768068	0.7990861	1.9
9	3.9958978	8.4275374	11.957372	12.425057	12.382291	11.879461	8.2463547	3.8556652	0.7680681	0.799086	1.9
3	3.995898	8.4275376	11.957372	12.425058	12.382292	11.879462	8.2463549	3.8556654	0.7680683	0.7990858	1.9
1	3.9958981	8.4275377	11.957372	12.425058	12.382292	11.879462	8.246355	3.8556655	0.7680684	0.7990857	1.9
2	10.71092	22.738763	32.334466	34.284854	34.365458	32.520272	22.442786	10.348904	1.9943397	2.4193443	4.5
7	3.9958976	8.4275372	11.957372	12.425057	12.382291	11.879461	8.2463545	3.855665	0.7680679	0.7990862	1.9
9	5.3494519	11.162553	15.827126	16.729861	16.765429	16.063125	11.085476	5.1125334	1.0136792	0.967402	2.3
8	10.710919	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365457	32.520271	22.442786	10.348904	1.9943393	2.4193448	4.5
2	10.71092	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365457	32.520271	22.442786	10.348904	1.9943394	2.4193446	4.5
7	10.710919	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365457	32.520271	22.442786	10.348904	1.9943392	2.4193449	4.5
6	10.710919	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365457	32.520271	22.442785	10.348904	1.9943391	2.419345	4.5
9	10.71092	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365457	32.520271	22.442786	10.348904	1.9943393	2.4193447	4.5
2	13.660999	29.012624	41.299914	43.878497	44.055626	41.563447	28.668825	12.965611	2.251421	3.5054541	5.9
8	13.660998	29.012624	41.299914	43.878497	44.055626	41.563447	28.668825	12.965611	2.2514208	3.5054542	5.9
4	10.710919	22.738762	32.334465	34.284854	34.365457	32.520271	22.442785	10.348904	1.9943389	2.4193451	4.5
3	3.9958982	8.4275379	11.957372	12.425058	12.382292	11.879462	8.2463552	3.8556657	0.7680686	0.7990855	1.9
9	3.9958979	8.4275375	11.957372	12.425058	12.382291	11.879461	8.2463548	3.8556653	0.7680682	0.7990859	1.9

Figure 111 – results of the PFS, % of overload respect to the cables' capacity

Five scenarios are simulated, in which the same methodology is applied:

- Scenario A (Baseline scenario) → this is the scenario which corresponds to the situation without the InvaDE technology to be used as baseline when comparing with the further scenarios. The InvaDE grid is considered without any batteries and with one PV system installed at each secondary substation.
- Scenario B → scenario in which the battery is charged during highest grid congestion (from 13:00h to 17:00h) at 50kW.

- Scenario C → scenario in which the battery is charged during highest grid congestion (from 14:00h to 16:00h) at 100kW.
- Scenario D → scenario in which the battery is discharged during highest grid congestion (from 14:00h to 16:00h) at 100kW.
- Scenario E (large scale) → scenario in which one battery is modelled in each substation. Battery discharge method is the same as scenario C.

Assumptions:

- The battery is charged in times of highest grid congestion (% of grid overload).
- Highest grid congestion is identified to be from 13h to 17h and it is a result of the baseline simulation, as it was during these four hours of the day in which the cables were most congested (figure X). The whole capacity of the battery is considered available to be used during the tests.
- The full capacity of the battery is considered available for the scenario simulations.
- The limit in which hosting capacity is calculated is the maximum grid overload (% of 50% of the cable rated current (330A).

Figure 112 – Invade grid drawn in Power Factory

Figure 113 – E.T.NODE in PowerFactory with PV and Battery simulated in PowerFactory

Figure 114 - Invade grid large scale simulation in Power Factory

6.8.2 Baseline (quantified)

The baseline scenario is the situation before implementing the Invade solution. Meaning that there is the Invade pilot MV grid, which includes 12 secondary substations and one

primary substation and has no storage assets installed available for providing flexibility. As mentioned previously, in this limited area of the grid there is no decentralized generation connected.

6.8.3 Reached value

The increase in hosting capacity was calculated according with methodology defined in the previous chapter and the results are presented in the table below.

Table 44 -increase in hosting capacity in different scenarios

Scenario	HostingCapacityLimit	Increase in hosting capacity [%]
A	11.9	-
B	12	$\frac{12-11.9}{11.9} = 0.84\%$
C	12.1	$\frac{12.1-11.9}{11.9} = 1.68\%$
D	12.6	$\frac{12.6-11.9}{11.9} = 5.88\%$

By adding one battery and PED in the E.T.NODE (scenario B) and charging it during the highest congestion peaks it implies an increase of about 0.84% in the hosting capacity of the whole grid of the pilot.

Scenario C considers a different charging method, in which the battery is charged at full capacity (100kW) during the two hours in which the stress on the cables is maximum. This scenario implies on an increase in the hosting capacity of the grid of about 1.68% when comparing with the baseline.

The last scenario simulates the existence of one battery and PED installed at each secondary substation and considers all batteries charge at full capacity during the two hours of most grid overload. This scenario implies on an increase in the hosting capacity of the pilot grid of about 5.88%.

6.8.4 Conclusion

It is concluded that under the current situation there is the potential of increasing the hosting capacity of the grid due to the Invade technology by about 1.68% with the existing technology and it could reach about 5.88% if considering the large-scale scenario with one battery installed in each substation.

It is proven that this technology has the potential to allow the increase on the share of renewables in the grid without need for adding new infrastructure.

6.9 Test 6: Grid investments reduction

The main objective of this indicator is to evaluate to a certain extent if there is an economic advantage for the DSO to make use of *flexibility* rather than investing in new infrastructure in the daily operations (or expansions) of the distribution grid.

6.9.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

The method chosen to make this indicator's analysis follows the outline of a cost-benefit analysis, starting by the identification and description of the two scenarios to be compared and proceeds to the costs/benefits breakdown and quantification.

The two scenarios identified in this test are:

- Scenario A (Baseline scenario) → It represents the current situation, where there is no possibility of using *flexibility* in the grid operations and the only option for the DSO to solve cases of technical issues or in cases of grid expansion is to invest in new infrastructure.
- Scenario B (Invade scenario) → represents the pilot scenario, where there is a FO which offers flexibility services to the DSO. The FO operates the battery through the Invade platform and sells flexibility to the DSO which uses it for managing the grid and backup purposes.

The costs and benefits breakdown are illustrated in Figure 115 and Figure 116. In scenario A, the costs undertaken by the DSO have two major components: the investments in grid infrastructure (cables, transformers, etc.) and a set of other costs which include environmental, societal, residual costs, etc.

To allow the scenario comparison, the geographical area and period of analysis must be the same in both cases. The geographical area consists of the MV grid of the Invade pilot, which is composed by 12 secondary substations and one primary substation. In this area, the infrastructure considered to be updated represents all transformers which are installed at each of the substations as well as the MV cables which connect them.

The cost breakdown of scenario B is highly dependent on the business model applied in the respective scenario. The costs' breakdown for this scenario consists on costs regarding flexibility use, costs of investment on the technology and (similarly as in scenario A) other costs. Depending on the business model adopted, these costs could be shared or distributed by the involved parties, in order to ensure benefit for all involved as well as contributing to the effective risk sharing of the model.

Figure 115 – outline of costs comparison between scenarios

The other important factor of the cost-benefit analysis is the breakdown of the existing/predicted benefits of each scenario. Figure 116 outlines this breakdown with a visual representation of both scenarios.

This scenario must be framed with the legal environment under which the DSO figure operates in Spain. Currently in Spain, DSOs are entities which are regulated by the government, they own and operate the medium and low voltage grid and are responsible for the delivering of electricity to the final customer. As it is a regulated environment, the government has a retribution scheme to ensure all O&M costs are paid within the electricity system, meaning they are included in the final price of electricity to the end customer.

There is therefore a retribution formula with which the yearly benefits to be paid to the DSO are calculated,

$$R_n^i = R_{n\ Base}^i + R_{n\ NI}^i + ROTD_n^i + Q_n^i + P_n^i(6)$$

Where,

- $R_{n\ Base}^i$ → consists on the base remuneration to be received by the DSO i at year n relative to all investment and O&M regarding electrical facilities commissioned until base year and that continue in service in year n-2. Base year is considered the year before the beginning of the regulatory period.
- $R_{n\ NI}^i$ → retribution for all new facilities (investment and O&M) commissioned after the base year and that continue in service in year n-2.
- $ROTD_n^i$ → retribution that the DSO i must receive in year n, for other regulated tasks overtaken in year n-2.

- $Q_n^i \rightarrow$ incentive/penalty to the quality of service (electricity supply) passed on to DSO i in year n associated to the quality indicators obtained by the respective company between years n-4 and n-2.
- $P_n^i \rightarrow$ incentive/penalty for the reduction of losses passed on to DSO i in year n, associated with power losses between years n-4 and n-2.
- $F_n^i \rightarrow$ incentive relative to the fraud reduction

The benefit breakdown is therefore composed by two main components: benefits due to retribution and other benefits. The other benefits consist in all benefits which may not represent directly a cash inflow for DSOs but rather produce benefits in the society, environment, or even consist on infrastructure which has a positive salvage value after the analysis period.

Figure 116 - outline of benefits comparison between scenarios

6.9.2 Baseline (quantified)

The baseline scenario is described above as scenario A.

6.9.3 Reached value

With the pilot implementation, the two major costs of each scenario were identified and are introduced in Figure 117. While in scenario A the costs undertaken by the DSO in investing in infrastructure are of 150,032.00€, the costs of investing in the Invade technology are 295,759.28€. Both costs include installation.

During the pilot implementation, costs regarding flexibility use and other costs were not quantified, and therefore the whole scale cannot be compared. However, the existing costs allow having a preliminary idea about the current situation under real market conditions.

Reached values are also interesting to be used under economical evaluations of business models, as to understand the different possibilities of CAPEX and OPEX responsibilities as well as risk sharing.

Figure 117 – costs quantification with data from the pilot implementation

Regarding the benefits, the quantification of each component does not depend so much on the adopted business model but rather on the estimations of how much would the improvements be in scenario B in comparison with scenario A.

The Invade implementation in the EPESA pilot is done mainly on a technical level as there is no legal framework in Spain which allows the conceived scenario to operate. As mentioned previously, the FO figure is not legal yet, and therefore this implementation has a real technical component and intends to extract the maximum conclusions to be implemented in further business models once the legal framework allows this type of solutions to operate. For this reason, quantifications regarding increments or reductions on the DSO retribution with the Invade pilot can only be done on a qualitative level and based on assumptions.

Regarding the retribution component of the benefits breakdown, it can therefore be identified that the parameters which could be influenced by the Invade pilot implementation are the Q_n^i and P_n^i which correspond to the penalties imposed to the DSO respect to the quality of service and incentives/penalties respect to power losses.

Under the current regulation scenario, the verification of the increase in the two parameters mentioned above are one of the major driving forces for DSOs to opt for solutions such as Invade. And certainly, would make economic sense for a DSO provided that these increments are higher than the costs over the same period.

6.9.4 Conclusion

This exercise is essential to understand that the concepts being tested in the pilot are inserted in a regulatory framework which do not incentivize this type of technologies and solutions to be implemented. With this indicator, it is also extracted the dimension of uncertainty regarding costs and benefits of this scenario and some possibilities for assumptions are noted down.

It is also concluded that, as important as verifying the technical viability of these type of concepts and solutions, is the verification of the economic conditions and businesses behind it. With the Invade pilot implementation, the technical solutions are validated which provide a good base for further understandings under which regulatory and business frameworks is it of best fit.

6.10 Test 7: Optimization Diesel Generation

The purpose of this test is to quantify the amount of CO₂ emissions avoided by not having to use the diesel generator as a backup system for the control centre room.

As mentioned previously, during the controlled islanding scenario, the battery will be used to supply the critical building with electricity for two hours. The main goal of this test is to understand the advantages of using a battery as backup service instead of the diesel generator, which is associated to expensive fuel costs and CO₂ emissions.

Therefore, this KPI's intention is to measure the % of decrease of CO₂ emissions from the diesel generator when supplying the critical building with electricity in islanding mode from the battery system.

6.10.1 Measurement procedure and (possible) range of values

In order to quantify the amount of CO₂ emissions avoided when using the battery to supply the control centre room in island mode there are identified two main situations in which the diesel generator is not being used thanks to having the battery. This situation are the yearly tests in which the diesel genset needs to be up and running to ensure its correct operation in case of urgent need and the situations in which there is an electric

failure and the genset needs to be turned on to supply the room with electricity while the failure is not overcome.

$$DecreaseCO_2 = \frac{CO_2(dieselgenerator) - CO_2(battery)}{CO_2(dieselgenerator)} \quad (7)$$

DecreaseCO₂: decrease in CO₂ emissions in a scenario with the flexibility operator comparing with a scenario without the flexibility operator (%)

CO₂(dieselgenerator): CO₂ emissions associated with using the diesel generator for the backup services (kg)

CO₂(battery): CO₂ emissions associated with using the battery for the backup services (kg)

6.10.2 Baseline (quantified)

The baseline scenario corresponds to the scenario in place before the Invade pilot, where the backup of the critical building is ensured by the diesel generator.

The emissions associated with this scenario were calculated based on the methodology proposed by WP3 and which detailed description can be seen in D3.4. Its quantification is also done by WP3 and can be viewed in D3.5. From this document the first variable is quantified,

$$CO_2(dieselgenerator) = 222 \text{ kg}$$

6.10.3 Reached value

The reached value of this indicator was calculated during LCA analysis, following the methodology proposed in D3.4 and being quantified in D3.5. The quantify of CO₂ produced by the battery is therefore,

$$CO_2(battery) = 77.84 \text{ kg}$$

Applying eq. 7 one can quantify the % of CO₂ emissions reduced when comparing the scenario with the FO with the baseline scenario. Using the battery for backup services instead of the diesel generator for one year implies the reduction of about 65% on CO₂ emissions.

$$DecreaseCO_2 = \frac{CO_2(dieselgenerator) - CO_2(battery)}{CO_2(dieselgenerator)} = \frac{222 - 77.84}{222} \cong 65\%$$

6.10.4 Conclusion

The main conclusion of this indicator is that from an environmental perspective the proposed solution of using the battery to provide backup service for the cox is more positive than the existing one of using a diesel genset, as it accounts for less 65% of CO₂ emissions.

In line with the current concepts being tested within the Invade project, this result is an indicator which values positively the benefits of offering this type of services to entities which possess critical buildings. Extending this result to a larger scale, in which a FO (or several FOs) manage and control a big volume of stationary batteries as storage assets and include backup services in their portfolio, it is positive to have the indication that from a sustainability point of view the offered solutions based on storage are more beneficial. It is, of course, always dependent on the case in which it is implemented, as it depends heavily on the genset and battery models and the times in which they are used, but the confirmation that for a pilot implementation with the current characteristics is advantageous from a sustainability point of view can be used as a selling point for a FO which wants to sell and promote this type of flexibility services.

In conclusion, and from an exploitation point of view, this result supports positively the FO business in selling backup services based on stationary batteries as flexibility assets.

7 Overall Conclusion

This document reflects the current status of the different pilots KPI tests and gives valuable feedback on the different pilots achieved results. The table below shows the status of all KPI's and pilots.

Table 45: KPIs summary in all pilots

KPI no	KPI	KPI description	Lyse	Greenflux/ Elaad	badenova	Albena	EPESA
1	Prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”	Standard defined methodology used to reduce time of adaptation in Scaling up the pilots. This KPI should prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”.					
2	Demonstrate the improvements using batteries	KPIs proving the reduction of the vulnerability in latency by using batteries in households. KPI= actual response / theoretical response with no latency					
3	Demonstrate peak reduction / cost – modern houses Vs old houses	KPI for sizing of the battery/inverter in new, efficient households VS old households, to improve efficiency and reduce power-peaks / costs. This KPI reflects the size in kWh vs. peaks. (lengths & heights) KPI = peak reduction / battery cost [kW/€]		NA		NA	NA
4	Valley filling: Smart Charging vs charging with fixed settings	To compare the models of charging with a fixed setting of the maximum capacity reflecting the limitation in the installation in worst case vs the Smart Charging model. Smart Charging using dynamic set points and predictions due to input from big data analytics			NA	NA	NA
5	V2G – DC/Chademo	Proving the new possibilities within the OCPP 2.0 and 15118 (ed. 2), giving the possibilities to balance the grid when including the reverse energy-flow.			NA	NA	NA
6	Optimize energy consumption based on hourly rate	As defined in D10.5, the purpose of this test is to compare the impact of switching off the low priority components when the energy price is high.		NA	NA	NA	NA
7	Optimize energy consumption based on effect/power	As defined in D10.5, the purpose of this test is to compare the impact of switching off the low priority components <u>when the consumption is high</u> .		NA	NA	NA	NA
8	Measure the improvement	This KPI will measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics)					

	t in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling by including a battery	cancelling of including a battery as part of an installation. This should be done at both for at household level, building level and on substation level.					
9	Increased share of renewable energy	The purpose is to show the impact of the smart charging algorithm on the amount of renewable energy that is used in EV-charging. Using the optimizing algorithm as designed in INVADE project.	NA		NA	NA	NA
10	KW max control for Grid connection	The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the smart charging algorithm on the kW-max of the grid connection. This is the maximum amount of energy that is consumed from the grid connection, measured in power output (kW).	NA		NA	NA	NA
11	APX-price effect	The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the prosumer optimization on the average energy price, as well as differences in the total electricity bill.	NA		NA	NA	NA
12	DSO Cost savings	To calculate the cost-savings for the DSO where we compare the costs of conventional grid reinforcement with investment cost in battery.	NA	NA		NA	NA
13	Additional revenues for private households	To make an analytic calculation what additional revenues for private households are necessary at least to convince them giving control over their devices to a flexibility operator	NA	NA		NA	NA
14	Frequency of flexibility usage	To make an analytic calculation, how many control signals are necessary over one year to receive results in peak-shaving	NA	NA		NA	NA
15	Cost savings from optimized energy flows	To prove real financial benefits from the adjusted power-flows. Albena will shift energy demand from high-priced hours on the day ahead-market to lower price-hours	NA	NA	NA		NA
16	Cost savings from increased RES share	To prove the increased share of RES leads to cost savings due to avoid grid energy demand.	NA	NA	NA		NA
17	% increased max power	To show the battery-impact for max-power control,	NA	NA	NA		NA
18	Stick to a predefined load profile	Controlling each 1-hour slot of a predefined 24-hour predefined profile	NA	NA	NA		NA
19	Congestion reduction issues	To evaluate the amount of congestion avoided in the pilot location over a certain	NA	NA	NA	NA	

		period by means of activating flexibility through a flexibility operator					
20	Energy and power loss-reduction	Calculated energy losses in the INVADE Spanish pilot	NA	NA	NA	NA	
21	Islanding time	To measure islanding time for the critical building in the Spanish pilot	NA	NA	NA	NA	
22	BRP cost savings	Self-balancing portfolio optimization with the aim of lowering the imbalance costs of the BRP, by activating flexibility.	NA	NA	NA	NA	
23	Capacity of the grid	Evaluate and quantify the % of increase in hosting capacity of the INVADE platform VS baseline.	NA	NA	NA	NA	
24	Grid investment reduction	Evaluate to a certain extent if there is an economical advantage for the DSO to make use of flexibility rather than investing in new infrastructure.	NA	NA	NA	NA	
25	Optimization to reduce diesel generation	Testing and quantifying the reduction of diesel generation. (CO2 reduction)	NA	NA	NA	NA	